

Supplementary material to the paper “The Importance of the Correlation in Crossover Experiments”

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Abstract—We present supplementary information and the data sets used in our analysis of the correlation between participants in software engineering experiments with human participants. The supplementary material is available online from <http://madeyski.e-informatyka.pl/download/KitchenhamMadeyskiScannielloGravinoTSEappendix.pdf>, as well as from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4475865> as Zenodo provides a more permanent link.

Index Terms—Formal experiments, crossover design, repeated measures correlation, experiments in software engineering.

1 INTRODUCTION

THIS paper includes supplementary information to support the paper [1]. In Section 2, we explain the underlying structure of the standard AB/BA crossover design and how the variance of the difference values (i.e., the difference between the observation obtained from each participant in the first time period and the observation on the same participant in the second time period) depends on the correlation between participant values in the two time periods. The variance of the difference values is required to conduct valid t -tests of the unstandardized effect size. In Section 3 we explain the structure of the 4 Group crossover. In Section 4, we present an example of calculating r values manually, and discuss how the functions we include in our \mathbb{R} reproducer package can be used to calculate r values and reproduce the majority of the data in Table 38 and Table 39. In Section 5, we present a table of the sample sizes needed to achieve 80% power for different values of r .

In Section 6 we summarise each of the 15 studies which provided us with experiment data on the distribution r -values. In Section 7, we present analyses of the r_p data that were omitted from the main paper due to lack of space. In Section 8 we present the details of the random effects analysis we undertook to check the extent to which treating the repeated r values caused by calculating the r

values for different metrics in the same experiment might be biasing our results. In Section 9, we present an analysis that demonstrates that statistical tools can take different approaches to assessing residual variation if r is negative. Finally, in Section 10, we present the variance and r -values calculated for each sequence group and each experiment. This data was the basis of our analyses in Section 4 of the main paper [1].

2 THE ROLE OF r IN THE ANALYSIS OF CROSSOVER DESIGNS

In an AB/BA crossover design, each participant has to perform two tasks. Participants in one group use technique 1 first and then technique 2 and participants in the other group use technique 2 first and then technique 1. This means that there are four experimental conditions to consider, as shown in Table 1.

In Table 1 we assume that B is control or baseline technique and A is the alternative technique and the improvement that using method A has over using method B is modelled by the parameter τ . π represents any *systematic* period effect due to the participants repeating a task in the second time period. Period effects are likely in SE experiments because the participants would not only use a different technique in the second time period, they would normally use a different program or documentation from another system. Assuming there is no interaction between the specific system and the particular technique (which is normal assumption underlying a crossover design [2]), we model the effect of the different system by the terms $S1$ and $S2$.

It is important to note that under each condition, the variance of the observations is assumed to be estimating the same underlying population variance (σ^2). σ^2 is interpreted as the variance of an individual doing a specific software engineering task (irrespective of the specific system and method being used).

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TABLE 1
The Structure and Expected Values and Variances for an AB/BA Crossover Design

Group	Period 1	Period 2	Difference (P1-P2)
G1	Technique A	Technique B	
$E(x_i)=\mu_i$	$m_2 = \mu_i + \tau + S1$	$m_1 = \mu_i + \pi + S2$	$\overline{Diff}_1 = \pi - \tau + S2 - S1$
Variance	$var(x_{p1}) = \sigma^2$	$var(x_{p2}) = \sigma^2$	$var(Diff)_1 = \sigma_{Diff}^2$
G2	Technique B	Technique A	
$E(y_i)=\mu_j$	$m_4 = \mu_j + S1$	$m_3 = \mu_j + \pi + \tau + S2$	$\overline{Diff}_2 = \pi + \tau + S2 - S1$
Variance	$var(y_{p1}) = \sigma^2$	$var(y_{p2}) = \sigma^2$	$var(Diff)_2 = \sigma_{Diff}^2$

Crossover designs are often viewed from the perspective of the difference values (i.e., the difference between the output value a participant achieved in period 2 and the output value the same participant achieved in period 1), see [2]. The importance of the difference value is that the effect due to individual participant differences is removed, leaving the expected value for the difference shown in the final column of Table 1. In this case, the estimate of the mean difference between the treatments (i.e., τ) is:

$$\hat{\tau} = \frac{(m3 - m4) - (m1 - m2)}{2} = \frac{\overline{Diff}_2 - \overline{Diff}_1}{2} \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{\tau}$ is the crossover unstandardized effect size. The estimate of $\hat{\tau}$ removes both systematic effects due to differences between time periods 1 and 2, systems and the impact of skill difference among participants.

If we consider the difference values, in each sequence group the difference values are derived from different participants and are, therefore, independent. The difference values in each group also estimate the same underlying population variance σ_{Diff}^2 . This means we can construct a t -test of the difference of the mean difference values to determine whether $2\hat{\tau}$ is significantly different from zero from the formula:

$$t = \frac{\overline{Diff}_2 - \overline{Diff}_1}{\sqrt{varDiff(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2})}} = \frac{2\hat{\tau}}{\sqrt{varDiff(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2})}} \quad (2)$$

where n_1 is the number of participants in sequence group G1, n_2 is the number of participants in sequence group G2 and $varDiff$ is the estimate of σ_{Diff}^2 obtained by pooling the the two variances $var(Diff)_1$ and $var(Diff)_2$. This is exactly the same as a standard between groups t -test. If $n_1 = n_2 = n$, $varDiff = (var(Diff)_1 + var(Diff)_2)$ and the t -test simplifies to:

$$t = \frac{2\hat{\tau}}{\sqrt{varDiff(\frac{2}{n})}} \quad (3)$$

This formulation of the t -test does not require an estimate of the correlation between the participant values. There is, however, a relationship between the σ_{Diff}^2 and σ^2 , that makes the relationship that r plays more obvious.

Statistical theory states that the variance of the difference of two correlated metrics, x and y , is:

$$\sigma_{diff}^2 = \sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 - 2cov_{xy} \quad (4)$$

where cov_{xy} is the covariance between the metrics and

$$cov_{xy} = \rho\sqrt{\sigma_x^2\sigma_y^2} \quad (5)$$

Since in the case of repeated measure of the same attribute on the same person, it usual to assume that $\sigma_x^2 = \sigma_y^2$ giving:

$$\sigma_{diff}^2 = 2\sigma^2(1 - \rho) \quad (6)$$

Then the t -test is calculated as:

$$t = \frac{2\hat{\tau}}{\sqrt{2s_{pooled}^2(1 - r)(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2})}} \quad (7)$$

where $2s_{pooled}^2$ is the estimate of σ^2 obtained by pooling the four variances obtained from the data in each of the four conditions shown in Table 1. If $n_1 = n_2 = n$:

$$t = \frac{\hat{\tau}}{\sqrt{s_{pooled}^2(1 - r)(\frac{1}{n})}} \quad (8)$$

which is the formula for the crossover t -test in [1].

3 THE 4-GROUP CROSSOVER DESIGN

The structure of a four group crossover is shown in Table 2. In effect the four group design comprises two AB/BA crossovers with the only difference being the order in which the different software materials are used.

Again the analysis of such a design can be based on the difference values. As with the AB/BA crossover, the variance of the difference values is $2s^2(1 - r)$ for each sequence group case which can be pooled to give the best estimate of the variance. In this case, the t -value is constructed from a linear combination of the mean differences from the four sequence groups:

$$t = \frac{\overline{Diff}_2 - \overline{Diff}_1 + \overline{Diff}_4 - \overline{Diff}_3}{\sqrt{2s_{pooled}^2(1 - r)(1/n_1 + 1/n_2 + 1/n_3 + 1/n_4)}} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\overline{Diff}_2 - \overline{Diff}_1 + \overline{Diff}_4 - \overline{Diff}_3 = 4\hat{\tau} \quad (10)$$

If we assume that all the n_i are all equal to n_{4G} , then for comparison with the two group crossover we let $n_{4G} = n_{2G}/2$, and we have:

$$t = \frac{4ES}{\sqrt{2s_{pooled}^2(1 - r)(8/n_{2G})}} = \frac{\hat{\tau}}{s_{pooled}^2(1 - r)(1/n_{2G})} \quad (11)$$

Thus, it appears that there is no practical difference between the standard AB/BA crossover and the four group extension. However, the four group design has two fewer degrees of freedom and the small sequence groups will systematically underestimate ρ (see the simulation results in the main paper).

TABLE 2
The Structure and Expected Values for Four Group Crossover Design

Group	Period 1	Period 2	Difference (P1-P2)
G1 x_i	Technique A $m_2 = \mu_i + \tau + S1$	Technique B $m_1 = \mu_i + \pi + S2$	$\overline{Diff_1} = \pi - \tau + S2 - S1$
G2 y_j	Technique B $m_4 = \mu_j + S1$	Technique A $m_3 = \mu_j + \pi + \tau + S2$	$\overline{Diff_2} = \pi + \tau + S2 - S1$
G3 x_{2h}	Technique A $m_6 = \mu_h + \tau + S2$	Technique B $m_5 = \mu_h + \pi + S1$	$\overline{Diff_3} = \pi - \tau + S1 - S2$
G4 y_{2k}	Technique B $m_8 = \mu_k + S2$	Technique A $m_7 = \mu_k + \pi + \tau + S2$	$\overline{Diff_4} = \pi + \tau + S1 - S2$

4 CALCULATING r

In this section, we present an example of how to calculate r from crossover data. We also discuss the R functions we provide in our `reproducer` package to facilitate both the construction of r values and the reproduction of the data presented in Table 38 and Table 39.

4.1 Example

The data set we use to illustrate how to calculate r_e , r_p and r_{exp} is the first experiment reported in study S2 (referred to as the EUBAS experiment). Details of study S2 can be found in Section 6.2. The basic data is shown in Table 3. It is presented in the *long* format, which means there are two row entries for each participant.

The data can be found in our R package `reproducer`, see `reproducer::KitchenhamEtAl.CorrelationsAmongParticipants.Scanniello14TOSEM`. The file contains data from all four experiments reported in S2 and has an extra column labelled *ExperimentID* which contains the identifier of each experiment. For the purpose of this example, we are not interested in the columns labelled *System* which specified the materials used in the experiment or *CrossOverId* which specifies which sequence groups are matched to form an AB/BA crossover. The columns labelled *Comprehension* and *Modification* are the outcome measures from the participants and are defined in Section 6.2. *Period* identifies in which time period the outcome measures were collected.

In order to calculate r_e and r_p it is necessary to convert from the long format to the wide format of the data. This is shown in Table 4. The terms *.1* or *.2* appended to the column names refers to the time period in which the observations were made, although the term is irrelevant for *SequenceGroup* because participants remain in the same sequence group for both parts of the experiment. So the first row specified that in the period 1 participant 1 used treatment AM and scored 0.77 for *Comprehension* while in time period 2, participant 1 used treatment SC and scored 0.53 for *Comprehension*.

In order to calculate r values we need to calculate the difference scores for each metric by subtracting the value of a metric in time period 1 from the value for the same participant observed in time period 2. For example, for participant 1, the difference value for *Comprehension* is $0.53 - 0.77 = -0.24$. The data in Table 5 show the data

used to calculate the r -values, where *CompDiff* and *ModDiff* are the difference values for *Comprehension* and *Modification*, respectively.

To calculate the r values, it is necessary to calculate the variance of each numerical value in Table 5. In the first four rows of Table 6 we show the sequence group variances for the *Comprehension* metric together with the r values. The exact r values are calculate using the formula:

$$r_e = \frac{VarCompT1 + VarCompTP2 - VarCompDiff}{2\sqrt{VarCompT1 \times VarCompTP2}} \quad (12)$$

where *VarCompT1* is the variance of the *Comprehension* metric values observed in the first time period, which are found in column labelled *Comprehension.1* in Table 5. *VarCompT2* is the variance of the *Comprehension* metric values observed in the second time period, which are found in column labelled *Comprehension.2* in Table 5. *VarCompDiff* is the variance of the difference between the *Comprehension* values observed in time period 2 and those found in time period 1, which are found in the column labelled *CompDiff* in Table 5.

Thus, for the *Comprehension* metric, the value of r_e , for sequence group A is:

$$r_e = \frac{0.018257 + 0.016310 - 0.044947}{2\sqrt{0.018257 \times 0.016310}} = -0.3007639 \quad (13)$$

which compares with the value of -0.3008 in the column labelled *r.e* in Table 6.

The pooled variance for each sequence group is the mean of the *VarCompTP1* and *VarCompTP2* values, i.e., for sequence group A, $VarCompPooled = (VarCompTP1 + VarCompTP2)/2 = (0.018257 + 0.016310)/2 = 0.0172835$ because the variances are obtained from the same participants in each time period. The pooled variance is used to construct the pooled r value:

$$r_p = \frac{2VarCompPooled - VarCompDiff}{2VarCompPooled} \quad (14)$$

Thus, the value of r_p , for sequence group A is:

$$r_p = \frac{2 \times 0.0172835 - 0.044947}{2 \times 0.0172835} = -0.3002864 \quad (15)$$

The value of r_p is in the column labelled *r.p* in Table 6 is -0.3003.

The column labelled *VP* in Table 6 is the proportion of the combined variance over the two time periods due to

TABLE 3
EUBAS Data

ParticipantID	SequenceGroup	System	Period	Treatment	Comprehension	Modification	CrossOverID
1	A	S1	1	AM	0.77	0.88	CO1
5	A	S1	1	AM	0.61	0.75	CO1
9	A	S1	1	AM	0.61	0.79	CO1
13	A	S1	1	AM	0.52	0.50	CO1
17	A	S1	1	AM	0.43	0.29	CO1
21	A	S1	1	AM	0.77	0.83	CO1
1	A	S2	2	SC	0.53	0.88	CO1
5	A	S2	2	SC	0.55	0.77	CO1
9	A	S2	2	SC	0.60	0.46	CO1
13	A	S2	2	SC	0.85	0.95	CO1
17	A	S2	2	SC	0.69	0.60	CO1
21	A	S2	2	SC	0.77	0.92	CO1
2	B	S1	1	SC	0.92	0.38	CO1
6	B	S1	1	SC	0.63	0.50	CO1
10	B	S1	1	SC	0.51	0.58	CO1
14	B	S1	1	SC	0.64	0.75	CO1
18	B	S1	1	SC	0.75	0.60	CO1
22	B	S1	1	SC	0.77	0.71	CO1
2	B	S2	2	AM	0.90	0.75	CO1
6	B	S2	2	AM	0.87	1.00	CO1
10	B	S2	2	AM	0.48	0.42	CO1
14	B	S2	2	AM	0.49	0.92	CO1
18	B	S2	2	AM	0.66	0.78	CO1
22	B	S2	2	AM	0.73	1.00	CO1
3	C	S2	1	AM	0.82	0.88	CO2
7	C	S2	1	AM	0.80	0.77	CO2
11	C	S2	1	AM	0.70	0.87	CO2
15	C	S2	1	AM	0.67	0.95	CO2
19	C	S2	1	AM	0.80	0.77	CO2
23	C	S2	1	AM	0.76	0.95	CO2
3	C	S1	2	SC	0.77	0.50	CO2
7	C	S1	2	SC	0.93	0.88	CO2
11	C	S1	2	SC	0.83	0.67	CO2
15	C	S1	2	SC	0.83	0.50	CO2
19	C	S1	2	SC	0.70	0.75	CO2
23	C	S1	2	SC	0.57	0.79	CO2
4	D	S2	1	SC	0.70	1.00	CO2
8	D	S2	1	SC	0.90	0.63	CO2
12	D	S2	1	SC	0.96	0.71	CO2
16	D	S2	1	SC	0.66	0.59	CO2
20	D	S2	1	SC	0.85	0.82	CO2
24	D	S1	1	SC	0.66	0.70	CO2
4	D	S1	2	AM	0.60	0.54	CO2
8	D	S1	2	AM	0.93	0.83	CO2
12	D	S1	2	AM	0.90	1.00	CO2
16	D	S1	2	AM	0.77	0.71	CO2
20	D	S1	2	AM	1.00	0.92	CO2
24	D	S2	2	AM	0.87	0.75	CO2

the variance of time period 1, it is a measure of variance stability. It is calculated using the equation:

$$VP = \frac{VarCompT1}{VarCompT1 + VarCompT2} \quad (16)$$

if the variance is stable across the time period VP will be close to 0.5. For sequence group A, we have $VP = 0.5282$ which reflects the fact that $VarCompT1$ and $VarCompT2$ are both close to 0.5. However, for sequence group C, we have $VP = 0.1922$ because $VarCompT1$ is much smaller than $VarCompT2$.

Table 38 shows the sequence variance and r values for all the studies and experiments we have analysed. The sequence group statistics shown in Table 6 correspond to those for study S2, experiment E1 and metric Comp in Table 38.

The final line Table 6 reports the experiment level variances and the value in the column labelled $r.p$ is the experiment level pooled variance which we refer to as r_{exp} in the elsewhere in this document. To obtain the experiment level variance data, we first pool the data across the sequence groups using the standard formula for pooling variances:

$$PooledVar = \frac{\sum_{i=1, \dots, k} (n_i - 1) Var_i}{\sum_{i=1, \dots, k} (n_i - 1)} \quad (17)$$

where k is the number of variances we want to pool and n_i is the number of observations used to construct the i th variance. In our case the EUBAS experiment is completely balanced with the same number of observations in each sequence group, so the equation for pooling the variance simplifies to obtaining the mean of the variances in each sequence group, i.e., the pooled variance for TP1, TP2, and the difference values and in Table 6 are the mean values of

TABLE 4
EUBAS data in the wide format

ParticipantID	Sequence-Group.1	System.1	Treat-ment.1	Compre-hension.1	Modifi.1-cation.1	System.2	Treat-ment.2	Compre-hension.2	Modifi-cation.1
1	A	S1	AM	0.77	0.88	S2	SC	0.53	0.88
5	A	S1	AM	0.61	0.75	S2	SC	0.55	0.77
9	A	S1	AM	0.61	0.79	S2	SC	0.60	0.46
13	A	S1	AM	0.52	0.50	S2	SC	0.85	0.95
17	A	S1	AM	0.43	0.29	S2	SC	0.69	0.60
21	A	S1	AM	0.77	0.83	S2	SC	0.77	0.92
2	B	S1	SC	0.92	0.38	S2	AM	0.90	0.75
6	B	S1	SC	0.63	0.50	S2	AM	0.87	1.00
10	B	S1	SC	0.51	0.58	S2	AM	0.48	0.42
14	B	S1	SC	0.64	0.75	S2	AM	0.49	0.92
18	B	S1	SC	0.75	0.60	S2	AM	0.66	0.78
22	B	S1	SC	0.77	0.71	S2	AM	0.73	1.00
3	C	S2	AM	0.82	0.88	S1	SC	0.77	0.50
7	C	S2	AM	0.80	0.77	S1	SC	0.93	0.88
11	C	S2	AM	0.70	0.87	S1	SC	0.83	0.67
15	C	S2	AM	0.67	0.95	S1	SC	0.83	0.50
19	C	S2	AM	0.80	0.77	S1	SC	0.70	0.75
23	C	S2	AM	0.76	0.95	S1	SC	0.57	0.79
4	D	S2	SC	0.70	1.00	S1	AM	0.60	0.54
8	D	S2	SC	0.90	0.63	S1	AM	0.93	0.83
12	D	S2	SC	0.96	0.71	S1	AM	0.90	1.00
16	D	S2	SC	0.66	0.59	S1	AM	0.77	0.71
20	D	S2	SC	0.85	0.82	S1	AM	1.00	0.92
24	D	S1	SC	0.66	0.70	S2	AM	0.87	0.75

the respective four sequence group variances. For example the Pooled value for TP1 *Comprehension* data variances is $(0.018257+0.020067+0.003697+0.017297)/4 = 0.0148295$. The pooled value of the TP1 and TP2 variances is the average of the two pooled variances, i.e., $(0.01483295 + 0.021143)/2 = 0.01798797$. Finally, r_{exp} is calculated using the method shown in Equation 14:

$$r_{exp} = \frac{2 \times 0.017986 - 0.024767}{2 \times 0.017986} = 0.3114923 \quad (18)$$

where r_{exp} corresponds to the value in the final row and column labelled $r.p$ in Table 6.

Table 39 includes the experiment level variances and r values for all the studies, experiments and metrics we have analysed. The data reported in the last row of Table 6 correspond to the data for the metric *Comprehension* in the row with the identifier S2E1 in Table 39.

4.2 Reproducibility

The preceding section explains how the r -values are calculated. However, with many studies, experiments and metrics it is tedious and error prone to calculate all the values by hand. We have provided three functions in our R `reproducer` package that can be used to calculate the values from studies containing data from all related experiments in a specific study, in the *long* format (see Table 3). The full data set must include a column labelled *ExperimentID* that identifies the experiment to which the data belong. For all studies with data belonging to authors of the paper, we include the available raw study data in the `reproducer` package. For example, the file `reproducer::KitchenhamEtAl.CorrelationsAmongParticipants.Scanniello14TOSEM` contains the data for study S2 [3].

```
# To make sure you use the correct version of reproducer remove any existing
version and re-install

remove.package(reproducer)
install.packages(reproducer)

# Read the study raw data from the reproducer package. For each study one or
more experiments are held in the same file in the long data format
dataset=reproducer::
KitchenhamEtAl.CorrelationsAmongParticipants.Scanniello14TOSEM

# Set up variables that hold details about the data
FullExperimentNames=c("EUBAS", "R1UCLM", "R2UCLM", "R3UCLM")
ShortExperimentNames=c("E1", "E2", "E3", "E4")
Metrics=c("Comprehension", "Modification")
Groups=c("A", "B", "C", "D")
Type=c(rep("4G", 4))
StudyID="S2"
Control="SC"

# Obtain experimental data for each experiment in the family and put the
data for each experiment into the wide format

ExpData= reproducer::
ExtractExperimentData(dataset, ExperimentNames=FullExperimentNames, idvar="Par
ticipantID", timevar="Period", ConvertToWide=TRUE)

# Calculate the correlations for each sequence group and each metric for
each experiment in the family

SequenceGroupTable=reproducer::ConstructLevel1ExperimentRData(Data=ExpData, S
tudyID=StudyID, ExperimentNames=ShortExperimentNames, Groups=Groups, Metrics=Me
trics, Type=Type, Control=Control)

# Calculate the experiment level correlations for each experiment and each
metric in the family

ExpTable=
reproducer::CalculateLevel2ExperimentRData(Level1Data=SequenceGroupTable, Gro
ups=Groups, StudyID=StudyID, ExperimentNames=ShortExperimentNames, Metrics=Metr
ics, Type=Type)
```

Fig. 1. R Script to Construct Variances and Correlations

Figure 1 show the R instructions needed to produce the sequence group and experiment level variances and correlations for the S2 study data. Function `reproducer::ExtractExperimentData` is used to extract the data from each experiment in study into a separate list items and convert the data from the long to the wide format (see Table 5). Function `reproducer::ConstructLevel1ExperimentRData` is used to construct the sequence group level variances and

TABLE 5
EUBAS Data Necessary to Construct r values

SequenceGroup.1	Comprehension.1	Modification.1	Comprehension.2	Modification.2	CompDiff	ModeDiff
A	0.77	0.88	0.53	0.88	-0.24	0.00
A	0.61	0.75	0.55	0.77	-0.06	0.02
A	0.61	0.79	0.60	0.46	-0.01	-0.33
A	0.52	0.50	0.85	0.95	0.33	0.45
A	0.43	0.29	0.69	0.60	0.26	0.31
A	0.77	0.83	0.77	0.92	0.00	0.09
B	0.92	0.38	0.90	0.75	-0.02	0.37
B	0.63	0.50	0.87	1.00	0.24	0.50
B	0.51	0.58	0.48	0.42	-0.03	-0.16
B	0.64	0.75	0.49	0.92	-0.15	0.17
B	0.75	0.60	0.66	0.78	-0.09	0.18
B	0.77	0.71	0.73	1.00	-0.04	0.29
C	0.82	0.88	0.77	0.50	-0.05	-0.38
C	0.80	0.77	0.93	0.88	0.13	0.11
C	0.70	0.87	0.83	0.67	0.13	-0.20
C	0.67	0.95	0.83	0.50	0.16	-0.45
C	0.80	0.77	0.70	0.75	-0.10	-0.02
C	0.76	0.95	0.57	0.79	-0.19	-0.16
D	0.70	1.00	0.60	0.54	-0.10	-0.46
D	0.90	0.63	0.93	0.83	0.03	0.20
D	0.96	0.71	0.90	1.00	-0.06	0.29
D	0.66	0.59	0.77	0.71	0.11	0.12
D	0.85	0.82	1.00	0.92	0.15	0.10
D	0.66	0.70	0.87	0.75	0.21	0.05

TABLE 6
Variances and r values for the EUBAS Comprehension Data

SequenceGroup	VarCompTP1	VarCompTP2	VarCompPooled	VP	VarCompDiff	r.e	r.p
A	0.018257	0.016310	0.017283	0.528158	0.044947	-0.30077	-0.30029
B	0.020067	0.032617	0.026342	0.380892	0.017950	0.67883	0.65929
C	0.003697	0.015537	0.009617	0.192201	0.021387	-0.14207	-0.11196
D	0.017297	0.020110	0.018703	0.462395	0.014787	0.60642	0.60471
Pooled	0.014829	0.021143	0.017986	0.412236	0.024767		0.31149

correlations for each metric and each experiment¹. Function `reproducer::CalculateLevel2ExperimentRData` is used to construct the experiment level variances and correlation for each metric and each experiment. We used these three functions to create Table 38 and Table 6.

5 THE IMPACT OF r ON SAMPLE SIZES

Table 7 reports the number of observations required to achieve a power level of 0.8 for crossover designs with different effect sizes and different values of r . Note that the N_c values in Table 7 assume that the data are normally distributed, each group has the same underlying variance σ^2 , the value of the σ^2 is known, and the crossover design has not introduced any additional variance due to interactions between techniques and sequence order. We do not advise actually using sample sizes as small as 10, even if you are sure that your effect size is large, because in the main paper, we show that estimates of sample parameters will be unreliable with such small sample sizes.

1. The function also calculates some variables not used in this study.

TABLE 7
Number of Participants Needed to Achieve a Power Level of 0.8

	Effect Size	0.25	0.5	0.8
Between Groups	N_b	393	64	26
	Sample Size	786	128	52
Crossover	r	N_c values		
	-0.7	334	54	22
	-0.5	295	48	20
	-0.25	246	40	16
	0	187	32	13
	0.25	147	24	10
	0.5	98	16	7
0.7	60	10	4	

6 STUDY INFORMATION

This section summarises the experiments performed in each paper and the reported results. We report the following information for each study:

- Study goal
- Information about each experiment including:
 - The basic crossover design (referred to as 2G corresponding to the standard AB/BA

crossover, or 4G corresponding to the four group crossover).

- Setting referred to as L (laboratory), I (industry).
- Number of participants.
- Participant types referred to as UG for undergraduate students, PG for graduates, MS for MSc students, PhD for PhD students, R for researchers, and Prac for practitioners. The discipline for students is reported, if known, where CS refers to Computer Science.

- The metrics used to measure outcome variables, commonly used metrics are defined below.
- The experimental materials participants used to perform the required software engineering tasks.
- The results of any meta-analytic aggregation performed if the studies included multiple experiments.
- The outcomes of statistics tests for each experiment and each metric (if reported).

Many of the studies used an outcome measure based on the answering a number of questions to assess effectiveness sometimes referred to as comprehension or correctness. To assess the results of answering a questionnaire, authors sometimes used a simple count of correct answers but in many situations the answers were open (e.g., to answer a question about what classes or methods are affected by introducing new functionality, several classes might need to be identified). In addition, authors wanted to distinguish between wrong answers and missing answers. Thus, they often adopted the use of the F-metric which is calculated as follows

$$F = \sqrt{\frac{NumCorrect}{NumAnswered} \times \frac{NumCorrect}{TotalNumAnswers}} \quad (19)$$

where $\frac{NumCorrect}{NumAnswered}$ measures the correctness (also referred to as *precision*) and $\frac{NumCorrect}{TotalNumAnswers}$ measures the completeness of the answers (also referred to as *recall*). Similarly, many studies measured time (in minutes) and constructed a measure of efficiency by dividing their effectiveness measure by time. We only define metrics within a specific study if the authors did not use the above definitions.

6.1 Study S1

Paper: Scanniello et al. 2015 [4]

Title: Link Analysis Algorithms for Static Concept Location: An Empirical Assessment

Goal: To assess whether a new technique (implemented as a Eclipse plug-in) for static concept location (proposed by the authors) supports users in identifying the places in the code where changes are to be made.

Number of crossover experiments reported: 1.²

Table 8 presents an overview of the setting and participants in the experiment.

Outcome metrics for the experiment: 3

Metric definitions:

² In our analysis, we used only one of the two experiments (USB2) because the other experiment (USB1) was a simple between groups design.

TABLE 8
Study S1 Experiment Information

Experiment ID	Design Type	Setting	Number of Participants	Participant Type
USB2	4G	L	24	UG

- Time: The total time to identify (four) bugs given their associated bug reports.
- Correctness: Correctly identifying a single change method as in the change set of the bug report.
- Efficiency: $\frac{Correctness}{Time}$

Note: Two controlled experiments were presented in the paper: the original one and a replication. The authors opted for a crossover design only for the replication.

Materials: the experimental objects were obtained from jEdit (ver. 4.2) and iTunes (ver. 1.10, www.atunes.org). Mappings between the bug reports and the changes that implemented the fixes were extracted from their repositories and bug tracking system.

Reported results achieved by participants when using the proposed concept location plug-in for the execution of the concept location tasks (CL) or not (NOCL):

- Time. The participants spent less time with CL than with NOCL.
- Correctness. The achieved correctness values show a clear tendency in favor of CL.
- Efficiency. The participants achieved better efficiency values when using CL.

The detailed results for the experiment are reported in Table 9.

TABLE 9
Study S1 Significance Testing Results

Experiment ID	Metric ID	Significance Test Results
USB2	Time	CL < NOCL (p=0.073)
USB2	Correctness	CL > NOCL (p<=0.01)
USB2	Efficiency	CL > NOCL (p<=0.01)

Reproducibility: The experiment data from the study can be found in the `reproducer` package, see `reproducer::KitchenhamEtAl.CorrelationsAmongParticipants.Scanniello15ESE`.

6.2 Study S2

Paper: Scanniello et al. 2014 [3]

Title: On the Impact of UML Analysis Models on Source-Code Comprehensibility and Modifiability

Goal: To investigate whether analysis models (AM) plus source code support better comprehension and modification of software systems than using only source code (SC).

Number of experiments reported: 4.

Table 10 presents an overview of the setting and participants in each experiment.

TABLE 10
Study S2 Experiment Information

Experiment ID	Design Type	Setting	Number of Participants	Participant Type
EUBAS	4G	L	24	MS (CS)
R1UCLM	4G	L	22	MS (CS)
R2UCLM	4G	L	22	MS (CS)
R3UCLM	4G	L	18	P

Outcome metrics for each experiment: 2.

Metric definitions:

- **Comp_Level.** This denotes the comprehension level of the source code achieved by a software engineer measured by the F-metric;
- **Modi_Level.** This denotes the capability of a maintainer to modify source code measured by the F-metric.

Materials: Each experiment used analysis models and the associated source code from two different systems:

- S1 A software system to sell and manage CDs/DVDs in a music shop;
- S2 A software system to book and buy theater tickets.

We selected two experimental objects within S1 and S2 keeping in mind a trade-off between complexity and relevance of the functionality chosen. Analysis models accompanied chunks of source code implementing the specific functionality of S1 and S2 comprised 463 and 378 LOCs (lines of code), respectively. The experimental object selected in S1 included 6 classes, while the other included 5. We removed the comments within the source code of the two chunks of S1 and S2 to avoid biasing the results. The analysis models for S1 contained a use case diagram, two use cases, a conceptual model (detailed information on each of the four selected classes was provided through a table that also included a short summary on the meaning and the role of the class), and two sequence diagrams (one was for the main success scenario, while the other was for a boundary condition). Similarly to S1, the S2 document comprised a use case diagram, two use cases, a conceptual model, and two sequence diagrams.

Reported results after aggregating results from each experiment:

- **Comp_Level.** On average, the participants achieved slightly better results when employing source code alone. Better median values for SC were achieved in all the experiments, except for E-UBAS. The difference in favor of SC is more evident for R2-UCLM and R3-UCLM.
- **Modi_Level.** In the three replications (i.e., R1-UCLM, R2-UCLM, and R3-UCLM), the participants achieved better results when using source code alone (see mean and median values). However, for E-UABS, the modifiability levels obtained by those participants employing UML analysis models was higher than

the level obtained by the participants using source code alone.

The results for each experiment are reported in Table 11.

TABLE 11
Study S2 Significance Testing Results

Experiment ID	Metric ID	Significance Test Results
E-UBAS	Comp_Level	SC > AM (p=0.944)
R1-UCLM	Comp_Level	SC > AM (p=0.335)
R2-UCLM	Comp_Level	SC > AM (p=0.001)
R3-UCLM	Comp_Level	SC > AM (p=0.105)
E-UBAS	Modi_Level	SC > AM (p=0.09)
R1-UCLM	Modi_Level	SC > AM (p=0.654)
R2-UCLM	Modi_Level	SC > AM (p=0.344)
R3-UCLM	Modi_Level	SC > AM (p=0.594)

Reproducibility: The experiment data from the study can be found in the `reproducer` package, see `reproducer::KitchenhamEtAl.CorrelationsAmongParticipants.Scanniello14TOSEM`.

6.3 Study S3

Paper: Abrahao et al. 2013 [5]

Title: Assessing the Effectiveness of Sequence Diagrams in the Comprehension of Functional Requirements: Results from a Family of Five Experiments.

Goal: To assess whether the comprehension of functional requirements improves when software models include UML sequence diagrams.

Number of experiments reported: 5.

Table 12 presents an overview of the setting and participants in each experiment.

TABLE 12
Study S3 Experiment Information

Experiment ID	Design Type	Setting	Number of Participants	Participant Type
Italy 1	4G	L	24	UG (CS)
Italy 2	4G	L	24	MS (CS)
Spain 1	4G	L	28	MS (CS)
Spain 2	4G	L	20	PhD
Spain 3	4G	L	16	Prac

Outcome metrics for each experiment: 1

Metric definitions: Comprehension measured using the F measure.

Materials: Each experiment used analysis models and the associated source code from two different systems:

- ECP An e-commerce platform from which CDs and books can be ordered via the Internet from an online catalogue (Italy 1, Italy 2, Spain 1).
- E-Plat A software system for the management of courses, lecturers, and students of a university (Italy 1, Italy 2, Spain 1).
- M-Shop software system for managing the sales in a music shop (Spain 2, Spain 3).
- Theater A software system for managing a theater's ticket reservations (Spain 2, Spain 3).

The participants received two experimental objects (containing a set of models with an attached comprehension questionnaire), the training material, and a post experiment survey questionnaire. The experimental objects were the models of functional requirements (i.e., use case, object model, dynamic model). The comprehension questionnaire included multiple-choice questions.

Reported results after aggregating results from each experiment:

- The mean comprehension scores obtained for the participants when using sequence diagrams (DM) were superior to those obtained when not using them (NODM).

The results for each experiment are reported in Table 13.

TABLE 13
Study S3 Significance Testing Results

Experiment ID	Metric ID	Significance Test Results
Italy 1	Comprehension	DM > NODM (p=0.26)
Italy 2	Comprehension	DM > NODM (p<0.001)
Spain 1	Comprehension	DM > NODM (p=0.027)
Spain 2	Comprehension	DM > NODM (p=0.017)
Spain 3	Comprehension	DM > NODM (p=0.01)

Reproducibility: The experiment data from the study can be found in the `reproducer` package, see `reproducer::KitchenhamEtAl.CorrelationsAmongParticipants.Abrahao13TSE`.

6.4 Study S4

Paper: Torchiano et al. 2017 [6]

Title: Do UML Object Diagrams Affect Design Comprehensibility? Results from a Family of Four Controlled Experiments.

Goal: To assess whether UML (Unified Modeling Language) object diagrams improve comprehensibility of software designs documented as UML class diagrams.

Number of crossover experiments reported: 3.

Table 14 presents an overview of the setting and participants in the experiment.

TABLE 14
Study S4 Experiment Information

Experiment ID	Design Type	Setting	Number of Participants	Participant Type
PoliTo2	4G	L	17	UG
UniBas1	4G	L	24	PG
UniGe1	4G	L	66	UG

Outcome metrics for all the experiments: Comprehension level. Outcome metric for UniBas1 and UniGe1: Comprehension effort.

Metric definitions:

- Comprehension level: For Polito2, the number of correct answers. For UniBas1 and UniGe1, the F-metric.
- Comprehension effort. The time to accomplish a comprehension task, obtained from the start and end times recorded by participants on the comprehension questionnaires.

Materials: The systems used in the experiments are:

- File System manager (FS). It handles folders, files, and links. Folders can contain other elements (e.g., files), while links refer to other elements in the file system (e.g., folders).
- Roads system (R). It handles maps made up of cities connected by means of roads. Each road starts and ends in a city. Furthermore, a road is characterised by a length.
- Train (T). It is a system to manage timetables, trains, and paths.
- Catalogue system (C). It collects category of items (e.g., cars) and items (e.g., car models) based on a set of features (e.g., number of doors).

In PoliTo2, only FS and T were administered to the participants, while in UniBas1 and UniGe1 all the four experimental objects were used.

Reported results are: Participants with different IT experience and UML familiarity achieved different levels of benefit from the use of the UML object diagrams. More experienced participants with a good UML familiarity benefited more from object diagrams in terms of comprehension than less experienced participants. That is, in a context where the software is developed/maintained by people with good UML experienced, object diagrams could be useful. For comprehension effort, results showed no substantial variations in the effort needed to accomplish a comprehension task.

The emphasis in the paper was on integration of the results from different experiments (which also included a between groups experiment) and tests of hypothesis for each experiment were not reported.

Note: in PoliTo2 and UniGe1, the participants were assigned to the four groups randomly. In UniBas1, the participants were assigned to the four groups on their GPA (Grade Point Average). In particular, high and low ability participants were equally distributed among the four groups.

Reproducibility: The experiment data from the study can be found in the `reproducer` package, see `reproducer::KitchenhamEtAl.CorrelationsAmongParticipants.Torchiano17JVLC`.

6.5 Study S5

Paper: Scanniello et al. 2014 [7]

Title: Distributed modeling of use case diagrams with a method based on think-pair-square: Results from two controlled experiments.

Goal: To investigate whether a new method based on think-pair-square and its implementation in a integrated communication/modeling environment (TPS approach) are as effective as traditional face-to-face (F2F approach) in the requirements elicitation. The experiment was restricted to

modeling high level functionality of a software system based on use case diagrams that include only user-goal use cases.

Number of experiments reported: 1. The experiment was a 2-group replicated experiment which took place over 4 time periods. I.e., the initial AB/BA crossover experiment was repeated with same participants in the same sequence groups but using different software materials.

Table 15 presents an overview of the setting and participants in each experiment. In this experiment, the participants were organized into nine 4-person teams each comprising one MSc student and three undergraduate students.

TABLE 15
Study S5 Experiment Information

Experiment ID	Design Type	Setting	Number of Participants	Participant Type
Experiment	2G	L	36 (9 teams)	Mixed

Outcome metrics for the experiment: 2.

Metric definitions:

- Time. The time in minutes all the participants in a specific team spent on the requirement elicitation task.
- Quality. The quality of the use case diagram produced was assessed by comparing the models produced by each team with an oracle (i.e., the correct use case diagram), in terms of actors/use cases (a/u) and dependencies (d). The F measure was calculated for both a/u and d. Quality was measured as the arithmetic mean of the two F measure values.

Number of participants: 36 participants organised in 9 four-person teams. Teams are the unit of the experimental analysis.

Materials:

The adopted design ensured that each team worked on two different experiment objects (i.e., Object1 and Object2) in two laboratory runs (i.e., Run1 and Run2). The teams were grouped into sequence groups A and B.

For the first run of the experiment, Object1 is Library (a software system to manage books and users of a library), while Object2 is FilmCollection (a software system for the selling and the rental of films within a shop). For the second part of the experiment, Object1 and Object2 were Rent (a car rental software to manage available cars, customers, and reservations) and ECP (an E-Commerce Platform to order CDs and books via the Internet from an on line catalogue), respectively.

The size of the text within these document was nearly the same for all the systems (about 300 words and 2100 chars).

Reported results from each part of experiment:

- Average time to accomplish the tasks using TPS was much greater than the mean time to accomplish the same tasks with F2F, for both parts of the experiment.
- The teams achieved on average slightly better scores using F2F in the first part of the experiment and with TPS in the second part of the experiment.

The results for each part of the experiment are reported in Table 16.

TABLE 16
Study S5 Significance Testing Results

Experiment ID	Metric ID	Significance Test Results
Exp Part 1	Quality	TPS > F2F (p=0.371)
Exp Part 2	Quality	TPS > F2F (p=0.175)
Exp Part 1	Time	TPS > F2F (p<0.001)
Exp Part 2	Time	TPS > F2F (p<0.001)

Reproducibility: The experiment data from the study can be found in the `reproducer` package, see `reproducer::KitchenhamEtAl.CorrelationsAmongParticipants.Scanniello14JVLC`.

To reproduce the r values we used, it is necessary to obtain the r -values from each part of the experiment and take the averages.

6.6 Study S6

Paper: Scanniello et al. 2014 [8]

Title: On the Effect of Using SysML Requirement Diagrams to Comprehend Requirements: Results from Two Controlled Experiments.

Goal: to investigate whether requirements diagrams in SysML provide additional benefits compared to the standard UML use case diagrams for understanding requirements.

Number of experiments reported: 2.

Table 17 presents an overview of the setting and participants in each experiment.

Outcome metrics for each experiment: 2.

Metric definitions:

- Comprehension. The number of correct responses divided by the number of questions in the comprehension questionnaire.
- Completion time. Each participant recorded the start and end times on the paper copy of that questionnaire

Materials: The following two systems were used as the objects in the original experiment and its replication:

- Automobile. It is a mock-up of software for controlling car behavior with use cases about entering the car, anti-lock breaking or operating the climate control of a car.
- ESS (Enhanced Security System). The system is designed to detect potential intruders. When an intruder is detected, the operators of the central monitoring station contact the local police or security companies, warning them of the intrusion. The use cases include providing medical/intruder/fire emergency response or investigative data.

The materials available for the participants were: (i) a problem statement; (ii) the list of the non-functional requirements together with their unstructured textual descriptions; (iii) two requirement diagrams; (iv) a use case diagram

TABLE 17
Study 6 Experiment Information

Experiment ID	Design Type	Setting	Number of Participants	Participant Type
E-UBAS	2G	Laboratory	24	UG (CS)
R1-UGOT	2G	Laboratory	63	MS (CS, IT, SE)

together with the narratives of its use cases; and (v) descriptions of the actors. The Automobile system was specified using 16 non-functional requirements, while ESS was specified using 14. The number of use cases of Automobile and ESS were 8 and 5, respectively.

Reported results after aggregating results from each experiment:

- The mean comprehension scores obtained for the participants when using requirements diagrams (RD) were superior to those obtained when not using them (NORD).
- Average time to accomplish the tasks using NORD was slightly more than the mean time to accomplish the same tasks with RD.

The results for each experiment are reported in Table 18.

TABLE 18
Study S6 Significance Testing Results

Experiment ID	Metric ID	Significance Test Results
E-UBAS	Comprehension	RD > NORD (p<0.001)
R1-GOT	Comprehension	RD > NORD (p=0.556)
E-UBAS	Completion time	RD < NORD (p<0.001)
R1-GOT	Completion time	RD < NORD (p=0.805)

Reproducibility: The experiment data from the study can be found in the `reproducer` package, see `reproducer::KitchenhamEtAl.CorrelationsAmongParticipants.Scanniello14EASE`.

6.7 Study S7

Paper: Gravino et al. 2015 [9]

Title: Source-code comprehension tasks supported by UML design models: Results from a controlled experiment and a differentiated replication

Goal: To investigate whether the comprehension of object-oriented source-code improves when UML class and sequence diagrams produced in the software design phase are available.

Number of experiments reported: 2.

Table 19 presents an overview of the setting and participants in each experiment.

Outcome metrics for each experiment: 2.

Metric definitions:

- Comprehension: The number of correct answers to a comprehension questionnaire
- Completion time: Recorded directly by the participants reporting their start and finish times.

TABLE 19
Study S7 Experiment Information

Experiment ID	Design Type	Setting	Number of Participants	Participant Type
UniSA	4G	L	16	MS (CS)
UniBas	4G	L	16	UG (CS)

Materials: The systems used in both the experiments are:

- Music Shop. It is a system for handling the sales of a music shop.
- Theater ticket. It is a system for managing the reservation of Reservation: theater tickets.

Two experimental objects were selected which were similar in terms of size and complexity. For Music Shop, we selected a chunk of 463 LOCs as the experimental object (S1, from here on). The class diagram of the experimental object contained 6 classes, 27 attributes, and 45 methods. The sequence diagram depicted 1 actor, 5 objects, and 11 messages. For Theater, we selected a chunk of 378 LOCs as the experimental object (S2, from here on). The associated class diagram contained 5 classes, 22 attributes, and 36 methods, while the sequence diagram had 1 actor, 5 objects, and 9 messages.

Reported results after aggregation were:

- The mean comprehension scores obtained for the participants when using software design models (Mo) were superior to those obtained when not using them (NOMo) for UniSA, while with less experienced participants (UniBas) the mean comprehension achieved using Mo and NOMo is comparable.
- The mean completion time obtained for the participants when using software design models (Mo) were superior to those obtained when not using them (NOMo).

The results for each experiment are reported in Table 20.

TABLE 20
Study S7 Significance Testing Results

Experiment ID	Metric ID	Significance Test Results
UniSA	Comprehension	Mo > NOMo (p<0.01)
UniBas	Comprehension	Mo = NOMo (p=0.57)
UniSA	Completion time	Mo > NOMo (p=0.12)
UniBas	Completion time	Mo > NOMo (p<0.01)

Reproducibility: The experiment data from the study can be found in the `reproducer` package, see `reproducer::KitchenhamEtAl.CorrelationsAmongParticipants.Gravinol15JVLC`.

The first experiment in this study only reports r -values for Comprehension for three of the 4 sequence groups. This is because the difference values for sequence group D were zero, meaning the variance of the difference values was zero and r could not be calculated.

6.8 Study S8

Paper: Ricca et al. 2014 [10]

Title: Assessing the Effect of Screen Mockups on the Comprehension of Functional Requirements

Goal: To assess whether stakeholders benefit from the presence of screen mock-ups in the comprehension of functional requirements represented with use cases.

Number of experiments reported: 4

Table 21 presents an overview of the setting and participants in each experiment.

TABLE 21
Study S8 Experiment Information

Experiment ID	Design Type	Setting	Number of Participants	Participant Type
UniBas1	4G	L	33	UG (CS)
UniGe	4G	L	51	UG (CS)
PoliTo	4G	L	24	MS (CS)
UniBas2	4G	L	31	MS (Maths and Telecoms)

Outcome metrics for each experiment: 3

Metric definitions:

- Comprehension level: The proportion of correct answers obtained from a comprehension questionnaire.
- Task completion time. It was obtained from the reported start and finish times recorded on the questionnaire.
- Task efficiency. It is a derived measure that is computed as the ratio between comprehension level and task completion time.

Materials: requirement specification documents of two desktop applications.

- EasyCoin is a system for cataloguing collections of coins
- AMICO is a system for the management of condominiums

The specification documents of AMICO and EasyCoin contain 19 and 20 use cases, respectively. The number of screen mockups is 31 for AMICO and 32 for EasyCoin. The number of pages is 25 for both documents (using a 12 pt font when the screen mockups are present).

Reported results after aggregation were:

- The mean comprehension level obtained by participants using screen mark-ups (S) was superior to the ones obtained with text only (T);

- The mean task completion time spent by participants using S was lower to the ones obtained with T;
- The mean task efficiency obtained by participants using S was superior to the ones obtained with T;

The results for each experiment are reported in Table 22.

TABLE 22
Study S8 Significance Testing Results

Experiment ID	Metric ID	Significance Test Results
UniBas	Comprehension level	S > T (p<0.001)
UniGe	Comprehension level	S > T (p<0.001)
PoliTo	Comprehension level	S > T (p<0.001)
UniBas2	Comprehension level	S > T (p<0.001)
UniBas	Time	S < T (p=0.09)
UniGe	Time	S < T (p=0.18)
PoliTo	Time	S < T (p=0.06)
UniBas2	Time	S < T (p=0.03)
UniBas	Task efficiency	S > T (p<0.001)
UniGe	Task efficiency	S > T (p<0.001)
PoliTo	Task efficiency	S > T (p<0.001)
UniBas2	Task efficiency	S > T (p<0.001)

Reproducibility: The experiment data from the study can be found in the `reproducer` package, see `reproducer::KitchenhamEtAl.CorrelationsAmongParticipants.Ricca14TOSEM`.

The data from the UniGe were not available.

6.9 Study S9

Paper: Reggio 2015 [11]

Title: On the comprehension of workflows modeled with a precise style: results from a family of controlled experiments

Goal: to assess whether the level of formality/precision in workflow modeling, based on UML activity diagrams, influences two aspects of construct comprehensibility: correctness of understanding and task completion time.

Number of experiments reported: 2³

Table 23 presents an overview of the setting and participants in each experiment performed to compare the use of the precise style (Precise) in UML activity diagrams to model workflows against a well-known and widely used baseline style (i.e., the Ultralight style).

TABLE 23
Study S9 Experiment Information

Experiment ID	Design Type	Setting	Number of Participants	Participant Type
UniBZ	4G	L	26	MS (CS)
UniBA	4G	L	13	UG (CS)

Outcome metrics for each experiment: 2

Metric definitions:

- Comprehension level measured with the F-metric.

3. Actually, the paper contains 3 experiments, however one of them employed a completely randomized design (between groups) and so we could not include it in our analysis

- Comprehension time. It measures the time required to answer questions.

Materials: Two experimental objects (workflows) are the following.

- Process Order (PO). It processes orders for an online shop. It takes an order as input. The order can be accepted. Some information is filled in, then payment and shipment processes are accomplished. Finally, the order is closed.
- Document Management Process (DM). It manages the online review process of documents.

The UML activity diagram modeling PO comprises 16 nodes (8 actions, 2 object nodes, 1 fork, 1 join, 1 initial, 1 final, 1 decision, and 1 merge) and the UML activity diagram modeling DM comprises 15 nodes (6 actions, 4 object nodes, 1 initial, 2 final, 2 decisions).

Reported results after aggregating results from each experiment:

- The mean comprehension level obtained by participants using precise was superior to the ones obtained with ultra-light;
- The mean completion time spent by participants using ultra-light was lower than the ones obtained with precise.

The results for each experiment are reported in Table 24.

TABLE 24
Study S9 Significance Testing Results

Exp ID	Metric ID	Significance Test Results
UniBZ	Comprehension	Precise > Ultralight ($p < 0.01$)
UniBA	Comprehension	Precise > Ultralight ($p < 0.01$)
UniBZ	Time	Precise > Ultralight ($p = 0.89$)
UniBA	Time	Precise > Ultralight ($p = 0.15$)

Reproducibility: The experiment data from the study can be found in the `reproducer` package, see `reproducer::KitchenhamEtAl.CorrelationsAmongParticipants.Reggiol5SSM`.

6.10 Study S10

Paper: Madeyski 2010 [12]

Title: Test-Driven Development: An Empirical Evaluation of Agile Practice

Goals: To compare Test-First Solo Programming (TFSP) and Test-Last Solo Programming (TLSP) techniques with respect to: 1) external code quality measured by the Percentage of Acceptance Tests Passed (PATP), 2) the development speed measured by the Number of Acceptance Tests Passed Per Hour (NATPPH), 3) internal code quality measured by means of Coupling Between Objects (CBO), Weighted Number of Methods in Class (WMC), and Response For a Class (RFC).

Number of crossover experiments reported: 14.

4. In our analysis, we used only one (P2007 aka SMELLS&LIBRARY) of the three experiments because the other experiments (ACCOUNTING, SUBMISSION) were simple between groups designs.

Table 25 presents an overview of the setting and participants in the experiment.

TABLE 25
Study S10 Experiment Information

Experiment ID	Design Type	Setting	Number of Participants	Participant Type
P2007	2G	L	22	MSc (SE) (20 from industry)

Outcome metrics for the experiment: 5, although only 2 were used in this study.

Metric definitions:

- *PATP* is an indicator of external code quality calculated as the number of acceptance tests passed (NATP) divided (normalized) by the total number of acceptance tests.
- *NATPPH* is an indicator of development speed calculated as the number of acceptance tests passed per (development) hour.

Materials: Experimental materials for the experiment (including user stories, questionnaires, tools etc.) were prepared in advance with the help of software development company and were available to the participants via a WIKI-based web site dedicated to the experiment and assigned accounts in version control repositories. To enable proper measurement of the development time (necessary to attain goal 2) and to be able to check how the development techniques TFSP and TLSP were carried out (especially whether tests, when using the TFSP technique, were in fact written before related pieces of the production code), the Eclipse IDE plugin has been developed, tested beforehand [13], and used by the participants of the experiment.

During the experiment, participants developed two applications: 1) SMELLS – a tool for identifying bad smells in Java source code (i.e., bad code smells detector) using a set of software metrics and 2) LIBRARY – a library application to streamline the circulation of books owned by the IT company that was also responsible for preparing the requirements.

Reported results (briefly presented in Table 26) are as follows:

TABLE 26
Study S10 Significance Testing Results

Exp ID	Metric ID	Significance Test Results (Exact Sig., 2-tailed)
P2007	<i>PATP</i>	$p = 0.874$
P2007	<i>NATPPH</i>	$p = 0.463$

The percentage of acceptance tests passed (*PATP*) measured in the TLSP ($Mdn = 0.57$) and TFSP experimental group ($Mdn = 0.66$) was not significantly different (the Wilcoxon test statistics: $T = 121.00$, $p > 0.05$, $r = 0.03$).

Moreover, the effect size estimate ($r = 0.03$) indicates that there is a tiny (not substantive) effect of TFSP on *PATP*.

The TLSP ($Mdn = 0.80$) and TFSP ($Mdn = 1.19$) groups did not differ significantly in the number of acceptance tests passed per development hour (*NATPPH*), ($T = 103.00$, $p > 0.05$, $r = 0.12$). This effect size estimation indicates that the difference in *NATPPH*, due to the test-first (TF) practice followed instead of TL by solo programmers (SP), represents a small effect.

Reproducibility: The experiment data from the study can be found in the `reproducer` package and can be accessed as follows:

```
reproducer::KitchenhamEtAl.CorrelationsAmong
Participants.Madeyski10.
```

6.11 Study S11

Paper: Ricca et al. (2010) [14]

Title: How Developers' Experience and Ability Influence Web Application Comprehension Tasks Supported by UML Stereotypes: A Series of Four Experiments

Goal: To compare performances in comprehension tasks of participants when using source code complemented either by standard UML diagrams (UML) or by diagrams stereotyped using the Conallen notation (Conallen).

Number of experiments reported: 4.

Table 27 presents an overview of the setting and participants in each experiment⁵.

TABLE 27
Study S11 Experiment Information

Experiment ID	Design Type	Setting	Number of Participants	Participant Type
Exp 1	4G	L	13	MS (CS)
Exp 2	4G	L	20	UG (CS)
Exp 3	4G	L	10	MS (CS)
Exp 4	4G	L	8	R

Outcome metrics for each experiment: 1.

Metric definitions: Comprehension level measured using the F-metric.

Materials: Two Java-based Web applications, Claros and WfMS were considered to arrange experimental objects. Both were based on the Servlet/JSP technology and were small enough to fit the time constraints of the experimental sessions. The documentation included 19 UML classes (38 in Conallen's diagram) for Claros and 13 (24 in Conallen's diagram) for WfMS.

Reported results after aggregating results from each experiment:

- The mean comprehension level obtained for the participants when using stereotyped diagrams was superior to the ones obtained when standard UML diagrams.

The results for each experiment are reported in Table 28.

5. we considered the numbers of paired analysis performed in the paper. Indeed, the authors declare that some participants did not complete the second laboratory sessions

TABLE 28
Study S11 Significance Testing Results

Experiment ID	Metric ID	Significance Test Results
Exp 1	Comprehension	Conallen < UML (p=0.61)
Exp 2	Comprehension	Conallen > UML (p=0.04)
Exp 3	Comprehension	Conallen < UML (p=0.088)
Exp 4	Comprehension	Conallen > UML (p=0.31)

Reproducibility: The experiment data from the study can be found in the `reproducer` package and can be accessed as `fKitchenhamEtAl.CorrelationsAmongParticipants.Ricca10TSE`.

Although there were four experiments, they were run as two voluntary lab exercise sessions and some participants participated in only one of the sessions. This meant many of the crossovers were incomplete, and in many cases only one or two participants in a specific sequence groups completed the crossover.

Only the first two of the experiments had reasonable numbers of participants who completed both parts of the crossover, so although data from all the experiments can be found in the data file, we excluded the last two experiments from our study. It also means that the unmatched data from the first two experiments must be removed before calculating the r values.

6.12 Study S12

Paper: Scanniello et al. (2017) [15]

Title: Fixing Faults in C and Java Source Code: Abbreviated vs. Full-word Identifier Names

Goal: to investigate whether the use of abbreviated identifier names (ABBR) affects fault fixing in C and Java source code, compared with full-word identifier names (FULL).

Number of experiments reported: 4

Table 29 presents an overview of the setting and participants in each experiment.

TABLE 29
Study S12 Experiment Information

Experiment ID	Design Type	Setting	Number of Participants	Participant Type
UniBas	4G	L	49	UG (CS)
UniNa	4G	L	19	MS (CS)
PoliNa	4G	L	16	MS (CS)
Prof	4G	L	16	P

Outcome metrics for each experiment: 3

Metric definitions:

- 1) Time. It indicates the number of minutes to accomplish a fault fixing task;
- 2) Effectiveness: In terms of F-metric which takes into account the the correctness and completeness of the answers
- 3) Efficiency. It is a derived measure that is computed as the ratio between task effectiveness and task completion time.

Materials: Four applications were used in the first two experiments (i.e., UniBas and UniNa): Agenda of 609 LOC (It keeps track of personal contacts), GAS-Station of 649 LOC (It manages the main feature of a GAS station), Financial of 202 LOC (It is a command line option price calculator), and Hotel-Reservation of 458 (It manages room reservations for Hotels). Indeed, two applications were provided to participants in each laboratory session they performed. Two different applications were instead used in the other two experiments (i.e., PoliNa & Prof): AveCalc of 1388 (It is a desktop application written in Java that manages an electronic register (record book) for Master’s students) and LaTazza of 1215 LOC (It is a desktop application for a hot drinks vending machine).

Reported results after aggregating results from each experiment:

- the effect of Method (ABBR vs FULL) was not statistically significant for task completion time;
- there was not a statistically significant difference between task effectiveness achieved with ABBR and FULL;
- the effect of Method (ABBR vs FULL) was not statistically significant on task efficiency.

The results for each experiment are reported in Table 30. Significance tests were not reported at the experiment level. If means were similar and standard deviations relatively large compared with the mean difference, we report that $ABBR \approx FULL$. If mean differences looked relatively large compared with the standard error we report the direction of the mean difference.

TABLE 30
Study S12 Individual Experiment Results

Experiment ID	Metric ID	Subjective Assessment
UniBas	Time	$ABBR \approx FULL$
UniBas	Effectiveness	$ABBR \approx FULL$
UniBas	Efficiency	$ABBR < FULL$
UniNa	Time	$ABBR \approx FULL$
UniNa	Effectiveness	$ABBR \approx FULL$
UniNa	Efficiency	$ABBR < FULL$
PoliNa	Time	$ABBR \approx FULL$
PoliNa	Effectiveness	$ABBR \approx FULL$
PoliNa	Efficiency	$ABBR < FULL$
Prof	Time	$ABBR \approx FULL$
Prof	Effectiveness	$ABBR \approx FULL$
Prof	Efficiency	$ABBR < FULL$

Reproducibility: The experiment data from the study can be found in the `reproducer` package data file `KitchenhamEtAl.CorrelationsAmongParticipants.Scanniello10ACMTOTW`.

6.13 Study S13

Paper: Romano et al. (2017) [16]

Title: The Effect of Noise on Software Engineers’ Performance

Goal: To study if noise affects software engineers’ performance in: (i) comprehending functional requirements and (ii) fixing faults in source code.

Number of experiments reported: 1⁶.

Table 31 presents an overview of the setting and participants in each experiment.

Participants of the experiment (Exp1) were asked to perform comprehension tasks under two different conditions: NOISE (i.e., participants working in noise conditions) and NORMAL (i.e., participants working in normal conditions).

TABLE 31
Study S13 Experiment Information

Experiment ID	Design Type	Setting	Number of Participants	Participant Type
Exp1	2G	L	55	UG (CS)

Outcome metrics for each experiment: 2

Metric definitions:

- 1) F_c : The F-metric.
- 2) Avg: the average number of correct answers calculated assuming that the correct answers for question is evaluated as 1 if and only if the set of answers provided by the participants to the question i corresponds to the oracle for the question.

Materials: For Exp1, the chosen experimental objects were:

M-Shop (A system for managing the sales in a music shop) and Theater (A system for managing the reservation of tickets in a theater).

Reported results are:

- the descriptive statistics suggest that there is little difference between the participants in a NORMAL environment and in a NOISE increased environment with respect to F_c and Avg.

The results for each experiment are reported in Table 32.

TABLE 32
Study S13 Significance Testing Results

Experiment ID	Metric ID	Significance Test Results
Exp1	F_c	NORMAL < NOISE ($p=0.5179$)
Exp1	Avg	NORMAL < NOISE ($p=0.4312$)

Reproducibility: The experiment data from the study can be found in the `reproducer` package data file `KitchenhamEtAl.CorrelationsAmongParticipants.Romano18ESEM`. The data from the second part of the experiment are also available the data file, but were not used in our study.

6.14 Study S14

Paper: Fernandez et al. (2013) [17]

Title: Empirical validation of a usability inspection method for model-driven web development.

6. We considered only Exp1 used in [16] since the second experiment, i.e., Exp2, was performed by a subset of participants involved in Exp1.

Goal: to analyze the Web Usability Evaluation Process (WUEP) in order to evaluate it with regard to its effectiveness, efficiency, perceived ease of use, and perceived satisfaction in comparison to the Heuristic Evaluation (HE) from the viewpoint of a set of usability inspectors.

In our analysis we have focused on the experiments conducted to evaluate effectiveness and efficiency.

Number of experiments reported: 2.

Table 33 presents an overview of the setting and participants in each experiment.

TABLE 33
Study S14 Experiment Information

Experiment ID	Design Type	Setting	Number of Participants	Participant Type
E1	4G	L	32	MS (CS)
E2	4G	L	20	MS (CS)

Outcome metrics for each experiment: 2.

Metric definitions:

- 1) Effectiveness: which is calculated as the ratio between the number of usability problems detected and the total number of existing (known) usability problems.
- 2) Efficiency, which is calculated as the ratio between the number of usability problems detected and the total time spent on the inspection process.

Materials: The type of the used Web application was an intranet for Task Management to be used in the context of a software development company. Two different functional features (Task Management and Report Management) were selected for the composition of the experimental objects (O1 and O2). Each experimental object contains three Web artifacts: a Navigational Access Diagram (NAD), an Abstract Presentation Diagram (APD) model, and a Final User Interface (FUI), according to OO-H method [17].

Reported results are:

- WUEP was relatively more effective than HE when inspecting the usability of the experimental objects.
- WUEP was relatively more efficient than HE when considering the usability of the experimental objects.

The results for each experiment (i.e., Rep1 and Rep2) are reported in Table 34.

TABLE 34
Study S14 Significance Testing Results

Experiment ID	Metric ID	Significance Test Results
Rep1	Effectiveness	WUEP > HE (p<0.000)
Rep1	Efficiency	WUEP > HE (p<0.000)
Rep2	Effectiveness	WUEP > HE (p<0.000)
Rep2	Efficiency	WUEP > HE (p<0.000)

Reproducibility: The raw data from this study are not in the public domain. Researchers wishing to reproduce the *r* values and variances in Table 38 should seek permission

to access the data from Dr. Fernandez. Fernandez [17] discusses data from three experiments, but data was only available for the two replication studies.

6.15 Study S15

Paper: Laitenberger et al. (2001) [18]

Title: An Internally Replicated Quasi-Experiment Comparison of Checklist and Perspective Based Reading of Code Documents.

Goal: To compare checklist-based reading (CR) and perspective-based reading (PBR) methods as a means of detecting defects in code.

Number of experiments reported: 3

Table 35 presents an overview of the setting and participants in each experiment.

TABLE 35
Study S15 Experiment Information

Experiment ID	Design Type	Setting	Number of Participants	Participant Type
E1	2G	I	18 (9 teams)	P
E2	2G	I	20 (10 teams)	P
E3	2G	I	20 (10 teams)	P

Outcome metrics for each experiment: 4

Metric definitions:

- 1) Team defect detection effectiveness: The number of defects found by the two-person team divided by the total number of defects in the code modules.
- 2) Cost per defect for the detection phase: Defect detection effort of two participants divided by the number of defects found by the two person team without any meeting gains.
- 3) Cost per defect for meeting phase: The meeting effort of the two-person team divided by the number of defects found by the two person team without any meeting gains.
- 4) Cost per defect for the overall inspection: Detection effort plus meeting effort divided by the number of defects found by the two person team without any meeting gains.

Number of participants: 58 participants organised in 29 two-person teams. Teams are the unit of the experimental analysis.

Materials: Each experiment used two different code modules obtained from the company hosting the experiments, see Table 36.

Reported results after aggregating results from each experiment:

- 1) Team detection effectiveness (M1): PBR significantly better than CBR
- 2) Cost per defect for the detection phase (M2): PBR significantly better than CBR
- 3) Cost per defect for meeting phase (M3): PBR significantly better than CBR

TABLE 36
Study S15 Materials Information

Experiment ID	Period 1 Materials	Period 2 Materials
E1	Code Module 1 (375 Loc, 8 defects)	Code Module 2 (627 Loc, 9 defects)
E2	Code Module 3 (666 Loc, 10 defects)	Code Module 4 (915 Loc, 16 defects)
E3	Code Module 5 (375 Loc, 11 defects)	Code Module 6 (627 Loc, 11 defects)

- 4) Cost per defect for the overall inspection (M4): PBR significantly better than CBR

The results for each experiment are reported in Table 37. Reproducibility: The raw data from this group of experiments are not in the public domain. The values of the correlation for each experiment and each metric are reported in the paper [18] and shown in Table 39.

TABLE 37
Study S15 Significance Testing Results

Experiment ID	Metric ID	Significance Test Results
E1	M1	PBR > CBR (p=0.007)
E2	M1	PBR < CBR (p=0.10)
E3	M1	PBR < CBR (p=0.02)
E1	M2	PBR > CBR (p=0.11)
E2	M2	PBR < CBR (p=0.04)
E3	M2	PBR < CBR (p=0.23)
E1	M3	PBR > CBR (p=0.0004)
E2	M3	PBR < CBR (p=0.035)
E3	M3	PBR < CBR (p=0.016)
E1	M4	PBR > CBR (p=0.05)
E2	M4	PBR < CBR (p=0.02)
E3	M4	PBR < CBR (p=0.11)

7 ANALYSIS OF r_p ESTIMATES

Figure 2 shows the histogram and box plot of the r_p estimates, it suggests distribution of r_p estimates is similar to that of the r_e estimates shown in the main paper. The relationship between r_p and the number of participants in each sequence group and in each sequence group level is shown in Figure 3. This is similar to the relationship with number of participants observed among the r_e estimates.

8 RANDOM EFFECTS ANALYSES

We used a random effects analysis (REA) to check the extent to which assuming the r values were independent might be biasing our analysis results. Our data included r values obtained from the same participants but based on different outcome metrics which might be considered to be repeated values.

The results of the REA for the r_e , r_p and r_{exp} values are shown in Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6, respectively. The closer the Intercept estimate is to the raw mean of the data and the smaller the percentage of total variance that is attributed to the Intercept, the less is the bias introduced

Fig. 2. The Distribution of r_p

Fig. 3. The Relationship Between r_p estimates and Size

by treating the individual r values as independent. The Intercept estimates are compared with the raw mean values in Table 4 in the main paper [1] and are close to one another in all cases. Since the mean values from the raw data are unbiased, we believe the estimates of the median values can also be trusted.

The proportion of the total variance attributed to the repeated r values was 11.5% for r_e , 11.6% for r_p and 22.6% for r_{exp} . This suggests more bias is introduced assuming the r_{exp} values are independent than assuming the r_e and r_p values are independent. Furthermore, the bias is likely to affect the variance estimates, and hence will affect the estimate of the upper and lower bounds of the confidence interval. The estimates of the confidence intervals in Table 4

in the main table show that the REA leads to slightly larger standard errors than standard errors obtained from the raw data.

```

Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']
Formula: r ~ (1 | Id)
Data: dataset

REML criterion at convergence: 380.4

Scaled residuals:
  Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.3400 -0.6241  0.1453  0.7700  1.6436

Random effects:
 Groups Name      Variance Std.Dev.
 Id      (Intercept) 0.0309  0.1758
 Residual                0.2369  0.4867
Number of obs: 249, groups: Id, 124

Fixed effects:
              Estimate Std. Error t value
(Intercept)  0.21922    0.03502    6.26
    
```

Fig. 4. Linear Mixed Model Analysis of the r_e data

```

Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']
Formula: r.p ~ (1 | Id)
Data: dataset

REML criterion at convergence: 303.3

Scaled residuals:
  Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.5852 -0.6804  0.1222  0.7382  1.8406

Random effects:
 Groups Name      Variance Std.Dev.
 Id      (Intercept) 0.02277  0.1509
 Residual                0.17348  0.4165
Number of obs: 249, groups: Id, 124

Fixed effects:
              Estimate Std. Error t value
(Intercept)  0.20775    0.02999    6.928
    
```

Fig. 5. Linear Mixed Model Analysis of the r_p data

```

Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']
Formula: r.Exp ~ (1 | ExpID)
Data: L2dataset

REML criterion at convergence: 21.6

Scaled residuals:
  Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.02357 -0.58258  0.03819  0.63096  2.03463

Random effects:
 Groups Name      Variance Std.Dev.
 ExpID  (Intercept) 0.01710  0.1308
 Residual                0.05861  0.2421
Number of obs: 80, groups: ExpID, 37

Fixed effects:
              Estimate Std. Error t value
(Intercept)  0.27203    0.03522    7.725
    
```

Fig. 6. Linear Mixed Model Analysis of the r_{exp} data

We also undertook a REA of the impact of the size on the r values. For this analysis we constructed sequence group and experiment group size categories. The sequence group categories are defined in column 1 of Table 5 in the main paper [1]. For example, 13 estimates of r_e were based on sequence groups of only 3 participants, whereas 31 estimates of r_e were based on sequence group comprising 9 or more participants. The r_p estimates were obtained from the same

```

Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']
Formula: r ~ SeqGroupLev + (1 | Id)
Data: dataset

REML criterion at convergence: 390.2

Scaled residuals:
  Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.28490 -0.65488  0.08503  0.79096  1.69998

Random effects:
 Groups Name      Variance Std.Dev.
 Id      (Intercept) 0.03376  0.1837
 Residual                0.23619  0.4860
Number of obs: 249, groups: Id, 124

Fixed effects:
              Estimate Std. Error t value
(Intercept)  0.07532    0.15212    0.495
SeqGroupLev4  0.10918    0.16768    0.651
SeqGroupLev5  0.15944    0.17486    0.912
SeqGroupLev6  0.12444    0.16817    0.740
SeqGroupLev7 -0.03682    0.23697   -0.155
SeqGroupLev8  0.26464    0.18220    1.452
SeqGroupLev9+ 0.22980    0.18262    1.258
    
```

Fig. 7. Linear Mixed Model Analysis of the Sequence Group Size Effect for the r_e Data

```

Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']
Formula: r.p ~ SeqGroupLev + (1 | Id)
Data: dataset

REML criterion at convergence: 314.9

Scaled residuals:
  Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.4982 -0.6612  0.0512  0.6802  1.9117

Random effects:
 Groups Name      Variance Std.Dev.
 Id      (Intercept) 0.02429  0.1559
 Residual                0.17344  0.4165
Number of obs: 249, groups: Id, 124

Fixed effects:
              Estimate Std. Error t value
(Intercept)  0.13082    0.13007    1.006
SeqGroupLev4  0.03527    0.14337    0.246
SeqGroupLev5  0.08031    0.14951    0.537
SeqGroupLev6  0.05639    0.14379    0.392
SeqGroupLev7 -0.06247    0.20264   -0.308
SeqGroupLev8  0.18363    0.15577    1.179
SeqGroupLev9+ 0.16760    0.15613    1.073
    
```

Fig. 8. Linear Mixed Model Analysis of the Sequence Group Size Effect for the r_p Data

sequence groups, so were distributed across the sequence group size categories in the same way. The experiment size group categories are defined in column 1 of Table 6 in the main paper. For example, 16 r_{exp} values were calculated for experiments with 10 or fewer participants and 8 r_{exp} values were calculated for experiments with more than 41 participants.

The results of the analyses of the size group categories for r_e , r_p and r_{exp} are shown in Figure 7, Figure 8 and Figure 9, respectively. Interpreting these results, however, is not straightforward. The first term in the effect analysis labelled (Intercept) is the estimate of the mean effect of the first size category, which we refer to as the baseline. The estimate for each of the other size categories is the estimate of the *difference* between the effect of the baseline and the effect of each of the other categories. The standard error for the first category is what we normally assume to be a standard error. However, the standard error for the other size categories is the standard error of the difference estimate, which is based on the residual variance and the number of observations in the two size categories being compared.

```

Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']
Formula: r.Exp ~ L2ExpSizeLev + (1 | ExpID)
Data: L2dataset

REML criterion at convergence: 30.6

Scaled residuals:
  Min      1Q   Median      3Q      Max
-2.35085 -0.57439  0.02694  0.61706  1.75620

Random effects:
 Groups      Name                Variance Std.Dev.
 ExpID      (Intercept)  0.02007  0.1417
 Residual                    0.05780  0.2404
Number of obs: 80, groups: ExpID, 37

Fixed effects:
              Estimate Std. Error t value
(Intercept)  0.36726    0.08847  4.151
L2ExpSizeLev11-15  0.03219    0.16175  0.199
L2ExpSizeLev16-20 -0.16095    0.11220 -1.434
L2ExpSizeLev21-25 -0.13855    0.11424 -1.213
L2ExpSizeLev26-40 -0.11248    0.13189 -0.853
L2ExpSizeLev41+  -0.03316    0.14307 -0.232
    
```

Fig. 9. Linear Mixed Model Analysis of the Experiment Size Group Effect for the r_{exp} Data

Thus the t -value for the intercept identifies whether the baseline category was significantly different from zero. The t -values for subsequent size categories test whether the difference from the baseline is significantly different from zero.

Looking at the Figure 7 we can see that the mean effect of the baseline category is not significantly different from zero and none of the other difference values is significantly different from the baseline. This does *not* imply that the overall mean effect is zero, it implies that the size categories are not different from a baseline and, by chance, the baseline (i.e., the Intercept) effect was small. In the case of r_{exp} shown in Figure 9, the baseline was large, but again there was no significant difference between the baseline and the other categories.

To obtain values comparable to the descriptive statistics shown in Table 5 and Table 6 in the main paper [1], the (Intercept) term is the estimate for the first size category, the estimate for the other size categories is obtained by adding back the *difference*. For example, for r_e , the REA estimate for size category 3 is 0.07532, the estimate for size category 4 is 0.07532+0.10918=0.1845. Overall, as reported in the main paper, the REA estimates for r_e and r_{exp} are quite close to the raw averages.

Overall, the REA found similar mean values to the descriptive statistics obtained from the raw data. However, the variance estimates from the raw data are likely to slightly underestimate the true values (because the repeated estimates from the same participants are slightly less variable than estimates from different participants). In addition, the REA results showed that the effect of repeated measures was smaller for the r_e and $r - p$ values than the r_{exp} values. Thus any estimate bias will be smaller for r_e and r_p than for r_{exp} .

9 EXAMPLE OF TOOL CONTRADICTIONS IN CROSSOVER DATA ANALYSIS

Study S2 reports the results of analysing a family of four experiments, each one of which was a four-group crossover design. We report the analyses of two of those experiments,

one of which exhibited a positive r -value (i.e., the EUBAS experiment) and one of which exhibited a negative r -value (i.e., the R2UCLM experiment). Figure 10 shows the results of using the linear mixed model package. In particular, the *Random effects* residual variance is specified as 0.012218 which is exactly the same as the value reported by the repeated measures analysis as the *Error Within Residual* in Figure 11. In contrast, the linear mixed model analysis of R2UCLM shown in Figure 12 reports that *Random effects* residual variance is 0.0443, but the repeated measures analysis in Figure 13 reports the *Error Within Residual* to be 0.0502. This means that from the same data set, if r is negative, one analysis might lead to a significant effect and another might not and, in addition, the standardized mean difference effect sizes, which are based on the square root of the residual error, will be different.

```

Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']
Formula: Comprehension ~ Period + Treatment + Object + CO + (1 | ID)
Data: ExpData[[1]]

REML criterion at convergence: -39.7

Scaled residuals:
  Min      1Q   Median      3Q      Max
-1.57227 -0.64279  0.08184  0.65642  1.40687

Random effects:
 Groups      Name                Variance Std.Dev.
 ID          (Intercept)  0.005377  0.07333
 Residual                    0.012218  0.11054
Number of obs: 48, groups: ID, 24

Fixed effects:
              Estimate Std. Error t value
(Intercept)  0.625722    0.060679  10.312
Period       0.024894    0.032021  0.777
TreatmentSC  0.005106    0.032021  0.159
ObjectS2     0.006268    0.032133  0.195
COCO2       0.122083    0.043754  2.790
    
```

Fig. 10. Linear Mixed Model Analysis of EUBAS Data

```

Error: as.factor(ID)
      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)
CO      1  0.1789  0.17885   7.785 0.0107 *
Residuals 22  0.5054  0.02297
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*'
0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Error: Within
      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)
Period  1  0.00775  0.007752   0.634  0.435
Treatment 1  0.00025  0.000252   0.021  0.887
Object   1  0.00046  0.000465   0.038  0.847
Residuals 21  0.25658  0.012218
    
```

Fig. 11. Repeated Measures Analysis of Variance of EUBAS Data

10 DATA USED TO ANALYSE ESTIMATES OF r

The data extracted from each study at the level of individual sequence groups are shown in Table 38. The results reported in Table 38 were used to calculate the experiment level data shown in Table 39. The correlations and variances in Table 39 were calculated prior to rounding the data in Table 38 for printing.

```

Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']
Formula: Comprehension ~ Period + Treatment +
Object + CO + (1 | ID)
Data: ExpData[[3]]

REML criterion at convergence: 2.5

Scaled residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.8240 -0.5981 -0.1163  0.7493  2.0933

Random effects:
Groups   Name              Variance Std.Dev.
ID       (Intercept)  0.0000  0.0000
Residual                0.0443  0.2105
Number of obs: 44, groups: ID, 22

Fixed effects:
              Estimate Std. Error t value
(Intercept)  0.14764    0.11802   1.251
Period       0.15108    0.06373   2.371
TreatmentSC  0.25455    0.06346   4.011
ObjectS2     -0.12808    0.06373  -2.010
COCO2       0.03958    0.06373   0.621
    
```

Fig. 12. Linear Mixed Model Analysis of R2UCLM Data

```

Error: as.factor(ID)
      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)
CO      1  0.0171  0.01709   0.442  0.514
Residuals 20  0.7734  0.03867

Error: Within
      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value  Pr(>F)
Period  1  0.2913  0.2913   5.798 0.02637 *
Treatment 1  0.7127  0.7127  14.187 0.00131 **
Object   1  0.1790  0.1790   3.562 0.07448 .
Residuals 19  0.9545  0.0502

---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01
                 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
    
```

Fig. 13. Repeated Measures Analysis of Variance of R2UCLM Data

TABLE 38: Correlations from Available Datasets

St	Exp	Grp	Metric	Id	n	var1	var2	varp	VP	vardiff	r_e	r_p
S1	E1	A	Corr	S1E1A	6	0.26667	0.56667	0.41667	0.3200	0.16667	0.8575	0.8000
S1	E1	B	Corr	S1E1B	6	0.96667	0.96667	0.96667	0.5000	0.40000	0.7931	0.7931
S1	E1	C	Corr	S1E1C	6	1.20000	1.20000	1.20000	0.5000	2.80000	-0.1667	-0.1667
S1	E1	D	Corr	S1E1D	6	0.16667	1.60000	0.88333	0.0943	1.76667	0.0000	0.0000
S1	E1	A	Time	S1E1A	6	70.16667	371.76667	220.96667	0.1588	620.66667	-0.5533	-0.4044
S1	E1	B	Time	S1E1B	6	318.56667	141.90000	230.23333	0.6918	713.46667	-0.5950	-0.5494
S1	E1	C	Time	S1E1C	6	347.86667	1064.00000	705.93333	0.2464	629.46667	0.6430	0.5542
S1	E1	D	Time	S1E1D	6	147.76667	871.46667	509.61667	0.1450	1096.30000	-0.1074	-0.0756
S1	E1	A	Effi	S1E1A	6	0.00004	0.00009	0.00007	0.2798	0.00007	0.5535	0.4969
S1	E1	B	Effi	S1E1B	6	0.00008	0.00098	0.00053	0.0791	0.00055	0.8964	0.4839
S1	E1	C	Effi	S1E1C	6	0.00010	0.00070	0.00040	0.1270	0.00118	-0.6948	-0.4627
S1	E1	D	Effi	S1E1D	6	0.00004	0.00062	0.00033	0.0615	0.00069	-0.0745	-0.0358
S2	E1	A	Comp	S2E1A	6	0.01826	0.01631	0.01728	0.5282	0.04495	-0.3008	-0.3003
S2	E1	B	Comp	S2E1B	6	0.02007	0.03262	0.02634	0.3809	0.01795	0.6788	0.6593
S2	E1	C	Comp	S2E1C	6	0.00370	0.01554	0.00962	0.1922	0.02139	-0.1421	-0.1120
S2	E1	D	Comp	S2E1D	6	0.01730	0.02011	0.01870	0.4624	0.01479	0.6064	0.6047
S2	E1	A	Modi	S2E1A	6	0.05275	0.03835	0.04555	0.5790	0.07348	0.1958	0.1934
S2	E1	B	Modi	S2E1B	6	0.01847	0.04818	0.03332	0.2771	0.05083	0.2651	0.2373
S2	E1	C	Modi	S2E1C	6	0.00655	0.02438	0.01546	0.2118	0.04467	-0.5437	-0.4443
S2	E1	D	Modi	S2E1D	6	0.02222	0.02662	0.02442	0.4549	0.06952	-0.4253	-0.4236
S2	E2	A	Comp	S2E2A	6	0.01940	0.04250	0.03095	0.3134	0.04886	0.2271	0.2107
S2	E2	B	Comp	S2E2B	6	0.01982	0.01918	0.01950	0.5082	0.06696	-0.7173	-0.7172
S2	E2	C	Comp	S2E2C	5	0.09540	0.01452	0.05496	0.8679	0.05012	0.8034	0.5440
S2	E2	D	Comp	S2E2D	5	0.07463	0.00933	0.04198	0.8889	0.04517	0.7350	0.4620
S2	E2	A	Modi	S2E2A	6	0.01838	0.00567	0.01202	0.7642	0.03691	-0.6299	-0.5348
S2	E2	B	Modi	S2E2B	6	0.06030	0.01350	0.03690	0.8171	0.07579	-0.0349	-0.0270
S2	E2	C	Modi	S2E2C	5	0.09265	0.02255	0.05760	0.8043	0.07700	0.4179	0.3316
S2	E2	D	Modi	S2E2D	5	0.00938	0.07337	0.04138	0.1134	0.06493	0.3396	0.2153
S2	E3	A	Comp	S2E3A	5	0.03242	0.00912	0.02077	0.7805	0.05965	-0.5266	-0.4360
S2	E3	B	Comp	S2E3B	5	0.03855	0.03183	0.03519	0.5477	0.10908	-0.5524	-0.5499
S2	E3	C	Comp	S2E3C	6	0.00587	0.04712	0.02649	0.1107	0.04827	0.1419	0.0891
S2	E3	D	Comp	S2E3D	6	0.06430	0.06483	0.06456	0.4979	0.19470	-0.5078	-0.5078
S2	E3	A	Modi	S2E3A	5	0.01250	0.04257	0.02754	0.2270	0.03407	0.4552	0.3813
S2	E3	B	Modi	S2E3B	5	0.03667	0.02993	0.03330	0.5506	0.03743	0.4402	0.4380
S2	E3	C	Modi	S2E3C	6	0.06566	0.06016	0.06291	0.5218	0.18806	-0.4952	-0.4947
S2	E3	D	Modi	S2E3D	6	0.05086	0.03100	0.04093	0.6213	0.11350	-0.3984	-0.3865
S2	E4	A	Comp	S2E4A	5	0.03308	0.02797	0.03053	0.5419	0.02558	0.5830	0.5810
S2	E4	B	Comp	S2E4B	5	0.05228	0.02363	0.03796	0.6887	0.01357	0.8868	0.8212
S2	E4	C	Comp	S2E4C	4	0.04423	0.01289	0.02856	0.7743	0.02960	0.5762	0.4818
S2	E4	D	Comp	S2E4D	4	0.04682	0.02902	0.03793	0.6173	0.08380	-0.1078	-0.1048
S2	E4	A	Modi	S2E4A	5	0.03972	0.03830	0.03901	0.5091	0.04007	0.4865	0.4864
S2	E4	B	Modi	S2E4B	5	0.04637	0.01303	0.02970	0.7806	0.04363	0.3208	0.2655
S2	E4	C	Modi	S2E4C	4	0.02467	0.10189	0.06328	0.1949	0.14983	-0.2320	-0.1838
S2	E4	D	Modi	S2E4D	4	0.01103	0.10587	0.05845	0.0944	0.15583	-0.5696	-0.3330
S3	E1	A	Comp	S3E1A	6	0.02678	0.02311	0.02494	0.5368	0.02139	0.5728	0.5712
S3	E1	B	Comp	S3E1B	6	0.01255	0.01395	0.01325	0.4736	0.00212	0.9213	0.9200
S3	E1	C	Comp	S3E1C	6	0.04099	0.02888	0.03494	0.5867	0.00979	0.8731	0.8599
S3	E1	D	Comp	S3E1D	6	0.04186	0.04799	0.04492	0.4659	0.02703	0.7008	0.6991
S3	E2	A	Comp	S3E2A	6	0.00879	0.00636	0.00757	0.5801	0.01003	0.3425	0.3380
S3	E2	B	Comp	S3E2B	6	0.00710	0.01334	0.01022	0.3473	0.00560	0.7624	0.7259
S3	E2	C	Comp	S3E2C	6	0.01042	0.00291	0.00666	0.7818	0.00379	0.8663	0.7155
S3	E2	D	Comp	S3E2D	6	0.01151	0.01174	0.01162	0.4951	0.00547	0.7647	0.7647
S3	E3	A	Comp	S3E3A	7	0.01252	0.00176	0.00714	0.8765	0.02176	-0.7947	-0.5229
S3	E3	B	Comp	S3E3B	7	0.01212	0.01390	0.01301	0.4656	0.02914	-0.1204	-0.1201
S3	E3	C	Comp	S3E3C	7	0.00294	0.01582	0.00938	0.1567	0.02187	-0.2282	-0.1659
S3	E3	D	Comp	S3E3D	7	0.01176	0.01318	0.01247	0.4715	0.02369	0.0500	0.0499
S3	E4	A	Comp	S3E4A	5	0.00248	0.01240	0.00744	0.1667	0.01074	0.3727	0.2778
S3	E4	B	Comp	S3E4B	5	0.02066	0.00826	0.01446	0.7143	0.04545	-0.6325	-0.5714
S3	E4	C	Comp	S3E4C	5	0.00248	0.00579	0.00413	0.3000	0.00661	0.2182	0.2000
S3	E4	D	Comp	S3E4D	5	0.07686	0.02066	0.04876	0.7881	0.02314	0.9333	0.7627
S3	E5	A	Comp	S3E5A	4	0.00275	0.00758	0.00517	0.2667	0.00758	0.3015	0.2667
S3	E5	B	Comp	S3E5B	4	0.00758	0.02755	0.01756	0.2157	0.04614	-0.3814	-0.3137
S3	E5	C	Comp	S3E5C	4	0.03581	0.01860	0.02720	0.6582	0.01860	0.6939	0.6582
S3	E5	D	Comp	S3E5D	4	0.03512	0.00207	0.01860	0.9444	0.03857	-0.0808	-0.0370
S4	E1	A	Comp	S4E1A	6	0.00859	0.03627	0.02243	0.1915	0.04065	0.1191	0.0937
S4	E1	B	Comp	S4E1B	6	0.03488	0.00928	0.02208	0.7898	0.02701	0.4766	0.3884
S4	E1	C	Comp	S4E1C	6	0.01889	0.02039	0.01964	0.4809	0.01114	0.7168	0.7163

TABLE 38: Correlations from Available Datasets (continued)

St	Exp	Grp	Metric	Id	n	var1	var2	varp	VP	vardiff	r_e	r_p
S4	E1	D	Comp	S4E1D	6	0.01316	0.00393	0.00855	0.7699	0.01461	0.1727	0.1454
S4	E2	A	Comp	S4E2A	4	2.25000	0.33333	1.29167	0.8710	2.91667	-0.1925	-0.1290
S4	E2	B	Comp	S4E2B	5	0.50000	1.00000	0.75000	0.3333	1.50000	0.0000	0.0000
S4	E2	C	Comp	S4E2C	5	0.70000	1.00000	0.85000	0.4118	0.70000	0.5976	0.5882
S4	E2	D	Comp	S4E2D	3	1.33333	0.33333	0.83333	0.8000	2.33333	-0.5000	-0.4000
S4	E3	A	Comp	S4E3A	32	0.02931	0.03282	0.03107	0.4718	0.04176	0.3285	0.3279
S4	E3	B	Comp	S4E3B	34	0.04543	0.02601	0.03572	0.6359	0.05902	0.1807	0.1739
S5	E1	A	Qual	S5E1A	5	0.02158	0.01481	0.02266	0.5930	0.02344	0.3623	0.3560
S5	E1	B	Qual	S5E1B	4	0.00533	0.00879	0.00286	0.3776	0.00920	0.3597	0.3488
S5	E1	A	Time	S5E1A	5	1691.00000	820.00000	1825.75000	0.6734	1483.00000	0.4365	0.4094
S5	E1	B	Time	S5E1B	4	1378.00000	666.30000	666.00000	0.6741	1340.00000	0.3673	0.3444
S6	E1	A	Comp	S6E1A	6	0.04280	0.03457	0.03868	0.5532	0.00823	0.8987	0.8936
S6	E1	B	Comp	S6E1B	6	0.04280	0.00823	0.02551	0.8387	0.03457	0.4385	0.3226
S6	E1	C	Comp	S6E1C	6	0.04815	0.02346	0.03580	0.6724	0.13333	-0.9184	-0.8621
S6	E1	D	Comp	S6E1D	6	0.04650	0.04938	0.04794	0.4850	0.05638	0.4122	0.4120
S6	E1	A	Time	S6E1A	6	93.86667	129.60000	111.73333	0.4200	220.66667	0.0127	0.0125
S6	E1	B	Time	S6E1B	6	121.76667	21.06667	71.41667	0.8525	79.50000	0.6252	0.4434
S6	E1	C	Time	S6E1C	6	98.66667	77.46667	88.06667	0.5602	22.66667	0.8777	0.8713
S6	E1	D	Time	S6E1D	6	71.20000	34.66667	52.93333	0.6725	37.86667	0.6844	0.6423
S6	E2	A	Comp	S6E2A	10	0.05093	0.04187	0.04640	0.5488	0.08096	0.1282	0.1276
S6	E2	B	Comp	S6E2B	17	0.01566	0.02633	0.02099	0.3729	0.02990	0.2977	0.2879
S6	E2	C	Comp	S6E2C	28	0.03560	0.03588	0.03574	0.4980	0.05298	0.2588	0.2588
S6	E2	D	Comp	S6E2D	8	0.02894	0.02888	0.02891	0.5005	0.02548	0.5594	0.5594
S6	E2	A	Time	S6E2A	10	18.66667	29.21111	23.93889	0.3899	34.54444	0.2855	0.2785
S6	E2	B	Time	S6E2B	17	69.06618	13.98529	41.52574	0.8316	78.98529	0.0654	0.0490
S6	E2	C	Time	S6E2C	28	40.78704	28.99868	34.89286	0.5845	67.10053	0.0390	0.0385
S6	E2	D	Time	S6E2D	8	129.83929	24.83929	77.33929	0.8394	90.21429	0.5676	0.4168
S7	E1	A	Comp	S7E1A	4	2.66667	0.66667	1.66667	0.8000	0.66667	1.0000	0.8000
S7	E1	B	Comp	S7E1B	4	2.25000	3.66667	2.95833	0.3803	0.91667	0.8704	0.8451
S7	E1	C	Comp	S7E1C	4	8.00000	0.33333	4.16667	0.9600	5.66667	0.8165	0.3200
S7	E1	A	Time	S7E1A	4	36.66667	23.00000	29.83333	0.6145	3.66667	0.9642	0.9385
S7	E1	B	Time	S7E1B	4	11.66667	75.00000	43.33333	0.1346	136.66667	-0.8452	-0.5769
S7	E1	C	Time	S7E1C	4	1.00000	22.25000	11.62500	0.0430	27.58333	-0.4593	-0.1864
S7	E1	D	Time	S7E1D	4	28.66667	8.25000	18.45833	0.7765	31.58333	0.1734	0.1445
S7	E2	A	Comp	S7E2A	4	2.25000	2.00000	2.12500	0.5294	8.25000	-0.9428	-0.9412
S7	E2	B	Comp	S7E2B	4	1.00000	1.66667	1.33333	0.3750	4.66667	-0.7746	-0.7500
S7	E2	C	Comp	S7E2C	4	5.66667	0.25000	2.95833	0.9577	4.91667	0.4201	0.1690
S7	E2	D	Comp	S7E2D	4	1.58333	1.33333	1.45833	0.5429	0.91667	0.6882	0.6857
S7	E2	A	Time	S7E2A	4	114.00000	18.91667	66.45833	0.8577	44.91667	0.9475	0.6621
S7	E2	B	Time	S7E2B	4	36.91667	74.00000	55.45833	0.3328	161.58333	-0.4847	-0.4568
S7	E2	C	Time	S7E2C	4	125.33333	8.66667	67.00000	0.9353	71.33333	0.9507	0.4677
S7	E2	D	Time	S7E2D	4	38.66667	484.25000	261.45833	0.0739	416.91667	0.3873	0.2027
S8	E1	A	Comp	S8E1A	8	0.01982	0.02554	0.02268	0.4370	0.02286	0.5000	0.4961
S8	E1	B	Comp	S8E1B	8	0.01125	0.06554	0.03839	0.1465	0.04214	0.6379	0.4512
S8	E1	C	Comp	S8E1C	8	0.01982	0.04839	0.03411	0.2906	0.07714	-0.1441	-0.1309
S8	E1	D	Comp	S8E1D	9	0.03611	0.02444	0.03028	0.5963	0.03500	0.4301	0.4220
S8	E1	A	Effi	S8E1A	8	8.93541	2.37388	5.65465	0.7901	6.34157	0.5393	0.4393
S8	E1	B	Effi	S8E1B	8	1.85674	9.61357	5.73516	0.1619	7.05474	0.5226	0.3850
S8	E1	C	Effi	S8E1C	8	1.84398	23.97584	12.90991	0.0714	27.78567	-0.1478	-0.0761
S8	E1	D	Effi	S8E1D	9	4.66197	6.79122	5.72660	0.4070	5.38081	0.5396	0.5302
S8	E1	A	Time	S8E1A	8	84.50000	128.85714	106.67857	0.3960	21.64286	0.9186	0.8986
S8	E1	B	Time	S8E1B	8	67.69643	57.12500	62.41071	0.5423	49.14286	0.6085	0.6063
S8	E1	C	Time	S8E1C	8	54.98214	84.41071	69.69643	0.3944	103.35714	0.2645	0.2585
S8	E1	D	Time	S8E1D	9	118.52778	167.86111	143.19444	0.4139	187.02778	0.3522	0.3469
S8	E2	A	Comp	S8E2A	8	0.02332	0.04045	0.03189	0.3657	0.02587	0.6170	0.5943
S8	E2	B	Comp	S8E2B	8	0.01603	0.02879	0.02241	0.3577	0.04337	0.0339	0.0325
S8	E2	C	Comp	S8E2C	8	0.02915	0.02332	0.02624	0.5556	0.06414	-0.2236	-0.2222
S8	E2	D	Comp	S8E2D	7	0.04373	0.02721	0.03547	0.6164	0.07775	-0.0986	-0.0959
S8	E2	A	Effi	S8E2A	8	7.10418	5.31115	6.20766	0.5722	14.20588	-0.1457	-0.1442
S8	E2	B	Effi	S8E2B	8	1.85830	8.08879	4.97355	0.1868	7.17486	0.3575	0.2787
S8	E2	C	Effi	S8E2C	8	2.81114	17.59644	10.20379	0.1377	26.65266	-0.4440	-0.3060
S8	E2	D	Effi	S8E2D	7	5.28260	4.12167	4.70214	0.5617	7.75205	0.1770	0.1757
S8	E2	A	Time	S8E2A	8	162.98214	175.64286	169.31250	0.4813	139.41071	0.5887	0.5883
S8	E2	B	Time	S8E2B	8	131.64286	130.78571	131.21429	0.5016	65.42857	0.7507	0.7507
S8	E2	C	Time	S8E2C	8	83.14286	56.98214	70.06250	0.5933	159.12500	-0.1380	-0.1356
S8	E2	D	Time	S8E2D	7	82.57143	144.28571	113.42857	0.3640	105.57143	0.5556	0.5346

TABLE 38: Correlations from Available Datasets (continued)

St	Exp	Grp	Metric	Id	n	var1	var2	varp	VP	vardiff	r_e	r_p
S8	E3	A	Comp	S8E3A	6	0.01200	0.01367	0.01283	0.4675	0.02167	0.1562	0.1558
S8	E3	B	Comp	S8E3B	6	0.01467	0.01767	0.01617	0.4536	0.02300	0.2899	0.2887
S8	E3	C	Comp	S8E3C	6	0.01600	0.01767	0.01683	0.4752	0.03367	-0.0000	-0.0000
S8	E3	D	Comp	S8E3D	6	0.01067	0.01767	0.01417	0.3765	0.01367	0.5342	0.5176
S8	E3	A	Effi	S8E3A	6	3.39782	2.36577	2.88180	0.5895	10.27287	-0.7952	-0.7824
S8	E3	B	Effi	S8E3B	6	1.87629	4.78721	3.33175	0.2816	1.97388	0.7824	0.7038
S8	E3	C	Effi	S8E3C	6	1.49416	5.45576	3.47496	0.2150	7.18090	-0.0405	-0.0332
S8	E3	D	Effi	S8E3D	6	3.56368	3.69955	3.63161	0.4906	2.60270	0.6418	0.6417
S8	E3	A	Time	S8E3A	6	57.36667	160.56667	108.96667	0.2632	234.80000	-0.0879	-0.0774
S8	E3	B	Time	S8E3B	6	60.70000	91.76667	76.23333	0.3981	181.86667	-0.1970	-0.1928
S8	E3	C	Time	S8E3C	6	17.46667	28.56667	23.01667	0.3794	75.36667	-0.6566	-0.6372
S8	E3	D	Time	S8E3D	6	71.86667	117.06667	94.46667	0.3804	47.60000	0.7704	0.7481
S9	E1	A	Comp	S9E1A	4	0.06330	0.02390	0.04360	0.7259	0.03713	0.6436	0.5742
S9	E1	B	Comp	S9E1B	3	0.00520	0.01240	0.00880	0.2955	0.01560	0.1245	0.1136
S9	E1	C	Comp	S9E1C	3	0.01243	0.01763	0.01503	0.4135	0.02010	0.3366	0.3315
S9	E1	D	Comp	S9E1D	3	0.02830	0.02110	0.02470	0.5729	0.01120	0.7816	0.7733
S9	E1	A	Time	S9E1A	4	134.00000	15.00000	74.50000	0.8993	128.33333	0.2305	0.1387
S9	E1	B	Time	S9E1B	3	57.33333	92.33333	74.83333	0.3831	49.00000	0.6918	0.6726
S9	E1	C	Time	S9E1C	3	21.33333	1.33333	11.33333	0.9412	33.33333	-1.0000	-0.4706
S9	E1	D	Time	S9E1D	3	157.00000	140.33333	148.66667	0.5280	289.33333	0.0269	0.0269
S9	E2	A	Comp	S9E2A	8	0.01601	0.01001	0.01301	0.6152	0.02306	0.1173	0.1142
S9	E2	B	Comp	S9E2B	5	0.03505	0.00767	0.02136	0.8205	0.04165	0.0328	0.0252
S9	E2	C	Comp	S9E2C	5	0.01362	0.05152	0.03257	0.2091	0.03078	0.6487	0.5276
S9	E2	D	Comp	S9E2D	8	0.01115	0.01095	0.01105	0.5045	0.01181	0.4653	0.4653
S9	E2	A	Time	S9E2A	8	110.85714	120.57143	115.71429	0.4790	248.00000	-0.0717	-0.0716
S9	E2	B	Time	S9E2B	5	56.50000	30.30000	43.40000	0.6509	81.30000	0.0665	0.0634
S9	E2	C	Time	S9E2C	5	183.20000	25.70000	104.45000	0.8770	149.80000	0.4307	0.2829
S9	E2	D	Time	S9E2D	8	14.26786	21.07143	17.66964	0.4037	47.41071	-0.3481	-0.3416
S10	E1	A	PATP	S10E1A	10	0.05683	0.06994	0.06339	0.4483	0.01802	0.8625	0.8578
S10	E1	B	PATP	S10E1B	12	0.02578	0.06687	0.04633	0.2783	0.09924	-0.0794	-0.0711
S10	E1	A	NATP	S10E1A	10	3.26532	6.60044	4.93288	0.3310	8.13974	0.1859	0.1750
S10	E1	B	NATP	S10E1B	12	1.11413	0.09143	0.60278	0.9242	1.43821	-0.3645	-0.1930
S11	E1	A	FMea	S11E1A	4	0.05489	0.00409	0.02949	0.9306	0.05313	0.1952	0.0992
S11	E1	B	FMea	S11E1B	3	0.00570	0.00063	0.00317	0.9000	0.00823	-0.5000	-0.3000
S11	E1	C	FMea	S11E1C	3	0.01423	0.00010	0.00717	0.9930	0.01463	-0.1257	-0.0209
S11	E1	D	FMea	S11E1D	3	0.02910	0.02303	0.02607	0.5582	0.09373	-0.8034	-0.7980
S11	E1	A	Time	S11E1A	4	203.58333	322.91667	263.25000	0.3867	34.00000	0.9604	0.9354
S11	E1	B	Time	S11E1B	3	112.00000	233.33333	172.66667	0.3243	65.33333	0.8660	0.8108
S11	E1	C	Time	S11E1C	3	26.33333	7.00000	16.66667	0.7900	17.33333	0.5892	0.4800
S11	E1	D	Time	S11E1D	3	243.00000	399.00000	321.00000	0.3785	291.00000	0.5636	0.5467
S11	E2	A	FMea	S11E2A	7	0.02338	0.03236	0.02787	0.4195	0.04700	0.1589	0.1569
S11	E2	B	FMea	S11E2B	4	0.07749	0.03749	0.05749	0.6739	0.02070	0.8746	0.8200
S11	E2	C	FMea	S11E2C	5	0.03998	0.00368	0.02183	0.9157	0.04900	-0.2201	-0.1223
S11	E2	D	FMea	S11E2D	4	0.00067	0.02107	0.01087	0.0307	0.02520	-0.4625	-0.1595
S11	E2	A	Time	S11E2A	7	142.57143	361.47619	252.02381	0.2829	115.95238	0.8548	0.7700
S11	E2	B	Time	S11E2B	4	34.91667	125.33333	80.12500	0.2179	142.91667	0.1310	0.1082
S11	E2	C	Time	S11E2C	5	148.70000	183.30000	166.00000	0.4479	262.80000	0.2096	0.2084
S11	E2	D	Time	S11E2D	4	94.25000	272.66667	183.45833	0.2569	254.25000	0.3514	0.3071
S12	E1	A	Time	S12E1A	4	110.25000	169.58333	139.91667	0.3940	124.33333	0.5686	0.5557
S12	E1	B	Time	S12E1B	4	1558.00000	65.00000	811.50000	0.9600	2065.66667	-0.6955	-0.2727
S12	E1	C	Time	S12E1C	4	459.66667	728.00000	593.83333	0.3870	1067.66667	0.1037	0.1010
S12	E1	D	Time	S12E1D	4	344.66667	108.33333	226.50000	0.7609	817.66667	-0.9436	-0.8050
S12	E1	A	FMea	S12E1A	4	0.07583	0.01790	0.04687	0.8090	0.03900	0.7428	0.5839
S12	E1	B	FMea	S12E1B	4	0.00120	0.02420	0.01270	0.0472	0.01780	0.7052	0.2992
S12	E1	C	FMea	S12E1C	4	0.10000	0.01603	0.05802	0.8618	0.05537	0.7575	0.5228
S12	E1	D	FMea	S12E1D	4	0.01303	0.01790	0.01546	0.4212	0.02416	0.2216	0.2188
S12	E1	A	Effi	S12E1A	4	0.00003	0.00005	0.00004	0.4082	0.00003	0.7164	0.7042
S12	E1	B	Effi	S12E1B	4	0.00011	0.00003	0.00007	0.7540	0.00023	-0.7743	-0.6669
S12	E1	C	Effi	S12E1C	4	0.00006	0.00013	0.00009	0.3312	0.00001	0.9962	0.9377
S12	E1	D	Effi	S12E1D	4	0.00010	0.00003	0.00007	0.7753	0.00021	-0.6907	-0.5766
S12	E2	A	Time	S12E2A	4	214.00000	286.91667	250.45833	0.4272	130.25000	0.7479	0.7400
S12	E2	B	Time	S12E2B	4	1340.33333	336.91667	838.62500	0.7991	900.25000	0.5781	0.4633
S12	E2	C	Time	S12E2C	4	34.91667	745.66667	390.29167	0.0447	1016.25000	-0.7303	-0.3019
S12	E2	D	Time	S12E2D	4	167.33333	251.33333	209.33333	0.3997	514.66667	-0.2341	-0.2293
S12	E2	A	FMea	S12E2A	4	0.02583	0.00720	0.01651	0.7820	0.05983	-0.9827	-0.8115
S12	E2	B	FMea	S12E2B	4	0.00122	0.01389	0.00756	0.0810	0.00870	0.7777	0.4245

TABLE 38: Correlations from Available Datasets (continued)

St	Exp	Grp	Metric	Id	n	var1	var2	varp	VP	vardiff	r_e	r_p
S12	E2	C	FMea	S12E2C	4	0.02250	0.00357	0.01303	0.8632	0.03427	-0.4577	-0.3146
S12	E2	D	FMea	S12E2D	4	0.04876	0.03222	0.04049	0.6021	0.00240	0.9912	0.9704
S12	E2	A	Effi	S12E2A	4	0.00001	0.00014	0.00008	0.0823	0.00014	0.2211	0.1215
S12	E2	B	Effi	S12E2B	4	0.00004	0.00001	0.00002	0.8693	0.00005	-0.1027	-0.0692
S12	E2	C	Effi	S12E2C	4	0.00003	0.00001	0.00002	0.6442	0.00007	-0.7628	-0.7304
S12	E2	D	Effi	S12E2D	4	0.00014	0.00001	0.00007	0.9579	0.00017	-0.3984	-0.1600
S12	E3	A	Time	S12E3A	13	1018.69231580.02564	799.35897	0.6372	1656.60256	-0.0377	-0.0362	
S12	E3	B	Time	S12E3B	13	1521.06410943.35897	1232.211540.6172	1467.91026	0.4159	0.4044		
S12	E3	C	Time	S12E3C	11	1544.854551165.472731355.163640.5700	1372.36364	0.4986	0.4937			
S12	E3	D	Time	S12E3D	12	1066.56818696.81061	881.68939	0.6048	1214.78788	0.3182	0.3111	
S12	E3	A	FMea	S12E3A	13	0.01684	0.04289	0.02986	0.2819	0.07561	-0.2955	-0.2659
S12	E3	B	FMea	S12E3B	13	0.03771	0.03226	0.03498	0.5389	0.04066	0.4202	0.4189
S12	E3	C	FMea	S12E3C	11	0.03095	0.04340	0.03717	0.4162	0.02773	0.6361	0.6271
S12	E3	D	FMea	S12E3D	12	0.03973	0.03837	0.03905	0.5087	0.02715	0.6524	0.6523
S12	E3	A	Effi	S12E3A	13	0.00003	0.00002	0.00002	0.6738	0.00005	-0.0448	-0.0420
S12	E3	B	Effi	S12E3B	13	0.00023	0.00004	0.00013	0.8565	0.00011	0.8165	0.5725
S12	E3	C	Effi	S12E3C	11	0.00025	0.00018	0.00021	0.5758	0.00013	0.6988	0.6907
S12	E3	D	Effi	S12E3D	12	0.00004	0.00017	0.00011	0.1939	0.00016	0.3099	0.2451
S12	E4	A	Time	S12E4A	5	1517.2000070.30000	793.75000	0.9557	1447.20000	0.2148	0.0884	
S12	E4	B	Time	S12E4B	5	990.20000	53.80000	522.00000	0.9485	1111.70000	-0.1467	-0.0648
S12	E4	C	Time	S12E4C	5	1565.5000081.50000	823.50000	0.9505	992.00000	0.9169	0.3977	
S12	E4	D	Time	S12E4D	4	1112.666678.25000	560.45833	0.9926	1172.91667	-0.2714	-0.0464	
S12	E4	A	FMea	S12E4A	5	0.13113	0.10797	0.11955	0.5484	0.04488	0.8161	0.8123
S12	E4	B	FMea	S12E4B	5	0.00723	0.00782	0.00752	0.4804	0.01052	0.3012	0.3010
S12	E4	C	FMea	S12E4C	5	0.03527	0.00423	0.01975	0.8929	0.05207	-0.5146	-0.3182
S12	E4	D	FMea	S12E4D	4	0.13203	0.13140	0.13172	0.5012	0.00643	0.9756	0.9756
S12	E4	A	Effi	S12E4A	5	0.00023	0.00062	0.00042	0.2690	0.00024	0.8039	0.7129
S12	E4	B	Effi	S12E4B	5	0.00024	0.00069	0.00046	0.2533	0.00073	0.2499	0.2174
S12	E4	C	Effi	S12E4C	5	0.00094	0.00014	0.00054	0.8667	0.00054	0.7356	0.5000
S12	E4	D	Effi	S12E4D	4	0.00027	0.00079	0.00053	0.2545	0.00016	0.9739	0.8484
S13	E1	A	Fc	S13E1A	28	0.01718	0.01078	0.01398	0.6145	0.02238	0.2048	0.1994
S13	E1	B	Fc	S13E1B	27	0.02093	0.01865	0.01979	0.5288	0.01574	0.6033	0.6023
S13	E1	A	Avg	S13E1A	28	0.02501	0.01446	0.01974	0.6336	0.02907	0.2736	0.2636
S13	E1	B	Avg	S13E1B	27	0.01895	0.01959	0.01927	0.4918	0.01526	0.6042	0.6042
S14	E2	A	Effe	S14E2A	8	0.01178	0.00169	0.00674	0.8746	0.01531	-0.2053	-0.1360
S14	E2	B	Effe	S14E2B	8	0.01773	0.01849	0.01811	0.4895	0.01035	0.7143	0.7142
S14	E2	C	Effe	S14E2C	8	0.00803	0.00285	0.00544	0.7378	0.00218	0.9088	0.7995
S14	E2	D	Effe	S14E2D	8	0.00803	0.01786	0.01294	0.3100	0.00941	0.6882	0.6366
S14	E2	A	Effi	S14E2A	8	0.00327	0.00154	0.00241	0.6805	0.00158	0.7202	0.6717
S14	E2	B	Effi	S14E2B	8	0.00115	0.00270	0.00192	0.2985	0.00118	0.7570	0.6928
S14	E2	C	Effi	S14E2C	8	0.00146	0.00019	0.00082	0.8837	0.00132	0.3148	0.2018
S14	E2	D	Effi	S14E2D	8	0.00117	0.00085	0.00101	0.5777	0.00104	0.4925	0.4866
S14	E3	A	Effe	S14E3A	5	0.00833	0.01480	0.01156	0.3603	0.00710	0.7217	0.6929
S14	E3	B	Effe	S14E3B	5	0.00208	0.02071	0.01140	0.0913	0.03241	-0.7319	-0.4217
S14	E3	C	Effe	S14E3C	4	0.01726	0.00463	0.01094	0.7886	0.00907	0.7172	0.5856
S14	E3	D	Effe	S14E3D	5	0.00473	0.01527	0.01000	0.2365	0.02449	-0.2637	-0.2241
S14	E3	A	Effi	S14E3A	5	0.00236	0.00122	0.00179	0.6588	0.00376	-0.0551	-0.0522
S14	E3	B	Effi	S14E3B	5	0.00007	0.00676	0.00342	0.0105	0.00767	-0.5962	-0.1218
S14	E3	C	Effi	S14E3C	4	0.00208	0.00017	0.00112	0.9252	0.00179	0.3819	0.2009
S14	E3	D	Effi	S14E3D	5	0.00018	0.00154	0.00086	0.1023	0.00229	-0.5560	-0.3370

TABLE 39: Pooled r - values for Each Experiment

StID	ExpID	N	Metric	PooledV1	PooledV2	VarProp	PooledV	PDiffVar	r.Exp
S1	S1E1	24	Correctness	0.650	1.083	0.375	0.867	1.283	0.260
S1	S1E1	24	Time	221.092	612.283	0.265	416.688	764.975	0.082
S1	S1E1	24	Efficiency	0.000	0.001	0.099	0.000	0.001	0.070
S2	S2E1	24	Comprehension	0.015	0.021	0.412	0.018	0.025	0.311
S2	S2E1	24	Modification	0.025	0.034	0.421	0.030	0.060	-0.004
S2	S2E2	22	Comprehension	0.049	0.022	0.685	0.036	0.053	0.250
S2	S2E2	22	Modification	0.045	0.027	0.626	0.036	0.063	0.117
S2	S2E3	22	Comprehension	0.035	0.040	0.467	0.038	0.105	-0.391
S2	S2E3	22	Modification	0.043	0.041	0.511	0.042	0.100	-0.176
S2	S2E4	18	Comprehension	0.044	0.024	0.649	0.034	0.035	0.475

TABLE 39: Pooled r - values for Each Experiment (continued)

StID	ExpID	N	Metric	PooledV1	PooledV2	VarProp	PooledV	PDiffVar	r.Exp
S2	S2E4	18	Modification	0.032	0.059	0.353	0.046	0.089	0.022
S3	S3E1	24	Comprehension	0.031	0.028	0.517	0.030	0.015	0.744
S3	S3E2	24	Comprehension	0.009	0.009	0.524	0.009	0.006	0.655
S3	S3E3	28	Comprehension	0.010	0.011	0.468	0.011	0.024	-0.148
S3	S3E4	20	Comprehension	0.026	0.012	0.685	0.019	0.021	0.425
S3	S3E5	16	Comprehension	0.020	0.014	0.593	0.017	0.028	0.191
S4	S4E1	24	Comprehension	0.019	0.017	0.519	0.018	0.023	0.357
S4	S4E2	17	Comprehension	1.094	0.744	0.595	0.919	1.709	0.070
S4	S4E3	66	Comprehension	0.038	0.029	0.562	0.033	0.051	0.243
S5	S5E1	9	Quality	0.013	0.016	0.441	0.014	0.004	0.871
S5	S5E1	9	Time	1962.114	695.314	0.738	1328.714	1318.457	0.504
S5	S5E2	9	Quality	0.017	0.009	0.660	0.013	0.031	-0.224
S5	S5E2	9	Time	1151.257	812.971	0.586	982.114	1525.143	0.224
S6	S6E1	24	Comprehension	0.045	0.029	0.609	0.037	0.058	0.214
S6	S6E1	24	Time	96.375	65.700	0.595	81.037	90.175	0.444
S6	S6E2	63	Comprehension	0.032	0.033	0.487	0.033	0.048	0.267
S6	S6E2	63	Time	55.647	24.466	0.695	40.057	68.100	0.150
S7	S7E1	12	Comprehension	4.844	1.750	0.735	3.297	2.719	0.588
S7	S7E1	16	Time	19.500	32.125	0.378	25.812	49.875	0.034
S7	S7E2	16	Comprehension	2.625	1.312	0.667	1.969	4.688	-0.190
S7	S7E2	16	Time	78.729	146.458	0.350	112.594	173.688	0.229
S8	S8E1	33	Comprehension	0.022	0.040	0.355	0.031	0.044	0.298
S8	S8E1	33	Efficiency	4.336	10.554	0.291	7.445	11.425	0.233
S8	S8E1	33	Time	82.706	111.574	0.426	97.140	93.628	0.518
S8	S8E2	31	Comprehension	0.027	0.030	0.478	0.029	0.052	0.099
S8	S8E2	31	Efficiency	4.226	8.952	0.321	6.589	14.176	-0.076
S8	S8E2	31	Time	116.289	126.281	0.479	121.285	117.821	0.514
S8	S8E3	24	Comprehension	0.013	0.017	0.444	0.015	0.023	0.233
S8	S8E3	24	Efficiency	2.583	4.077	0.388	3.330	5.508	0.173
S8	S8E3	24	Time	51.850	99.492	0.343	75.671	134.908	0.109
S9	S9E1	13	Comprehension	0.031	0.019	0.618	0.025	0.023	0.550
S9	S9E1	13	Time	97.037	57.000	0.630	77.019	125.370	0.186
S9	S9E2	26	Comprehension	0.017	0.017	0.501	0.017	0.024	0.305
S9	S9E2	26	Time	83.394	55.250	0.601	69.322	136.012	0.019
S10	S10E1	22	PATP	0.040	0.068	0.368	0.054	0.063	0.420
S10	S10E1	22	NATPPH	2.082	3.020	0.408	2.551	4.454	0.127
S11	S11E1	13	FMeasure	0.029	0.007	0.815	0.018	0.044	-0.217
S11	S11E1	13	Time	152.602	249.713	0.379	201.157	94.370	0.765
S11	S11E2	20	FMeasure	0.033	0.024	0.582	0.029	0.038	0.330
S11	S11E2	20	Time	114.858	256.004	0.310	185.431	183.651	0.505
S12	S12E1	16	Time	618.146	267.729	0.698	442.938	1018.833	-0.150
S12	S12E1	16	FMeasure	0.048	0.019	0.714	0.033	0.034	0.488
S12	S12E1	16	Efficiency	0.000	0.000	0.558	0.000	0.000	0.126
S12	S12E2	16	Time	439.146	405.208	0.520	422.177	640.354	0.242
S12	S12E2	16	FMeasure	0.025	0.014	0.633	0.019	0.026	0.322
S12	S12E2	16	Efficiency	0.000	0.000	0.564	0.000	0.000	-0.095
S12	S12E3	49	Time	1281.286	835.561	0.605	1058.424	1435.121	0.322
S12	S12E3	49	FMeasure	0.031	0.039	0.444	0.035	0.044	0.376
S12	S12E3	49	Efficiency	0.000	0.000	0.581	0.000	0.000	0.513
S12	S12E4	19	Time	1308.640	56.477	0.959	682.558	1181.490	0.135
S12	S12E4	19	FMeasure	0.073	0.058	0.555	0.065	0.030	0.771
S12	S12E4	19	Efficiency	0.000	0.001	0.439	0.000	0.000	0.553
S13	S13E1	55	Fc	0.019	0.015	0.565	0.017	0.019	0.432
S13	S13E1	55	Avg	0.022	0.017	0.565	0.020	0.022	0.429
S14	S14E2	32	Effectiveness	0.011	0.010	0.527	0.011	0.009	0.569
S14	S14E2	32	Efficiency	0.002	0.001	0.572	0.002	0.001	0.585
S14	S14E3	19	Effectiveness	0.007	0.014	0.341	0.011	0.019	0.140
S14	S14E3	19	Efficiency	0.001	0.003	0.301	0.002	0.004	-0.091
S15	S15E1	9	M1				0.026		0.770
S15	S15E1	9	M2				577.441		0.620
S15	S15E1	9	M3				3.240		0.550
S15	S15E1	9	M4				719.849		0.650
S15	S15E2	10	M1				0.044		0.780
S15	S15E2	10	M2				510.308		-0.020
S15	S15E2	10	M3				8.940		0.480
S15	S15E2	10	M4				619.014		0.210

TABLE 39: Pooled r - values for Each Experiment (continued)

StID	ExpID	N	Metric	PooledV1	PooledV2	VarProp	PooledV	PDiffVar	r.Exp
S15	S15E3	10	M1				0.020		0.030
S15	S15E3	10	M2				158.508		0.030
S15	S15E3	10	M3				2.723		0.170
S15	S15E3	10	M4				353.816		0.270

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